

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Estrone

CHID: 22367 CASRN: 53-16-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J11

M4ID: 30007613

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.742 MAX_MED: 0.0804 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Androstene-3,17-dione

CHID: 24523 CASRN: 63-05-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N10

M4ID: 30007708

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.9 MAX_MED: 2.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethomorph
 CHID: 34545 CASRN: 110488-70-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I22
 M4ID: 30007600

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.245 MAX_MED: -1.22 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tebufenozide

CHID: 34948 CASRN: 112410-23-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C03

M4ID: 30008280

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.13 MAX_MED: -1.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Testosterone propionate

CHID: 36515 CASRN: 57-85-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C07

M4ID: 30008225

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.696 MAX_MED: -0.205 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Acetaminophen

CHID: 20006 CASRN: 103-90-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P21

M4ID: 30007801

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	506.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.98 MAX_MED: -1.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Acifluorfen

CHID: 20022 CASRN: 50594-66-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J03

M4ID: 30007605

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	493.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.32 MAX_MED: 2.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Allantoin

CHID: 20043 CASRN: 97-59-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P11

M4ID: 30007811

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	607.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.08 MAX_MED: -2.39 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Amitrole

CHID: 20076 CASRN: 61-82-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078020

M4ID: 30007826

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	532.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.01 MAX_MED: -1.51 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Aniline hydrochloride

CHID: 20091 CASRN: 142-04-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L10

M4ID: 30007908

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	500.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.66 MAX_MED: 3.62 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Methoxyaniline hydrochloride

CHID: 20093 CASRN: 20265-97-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G07

M4ID: 30008103

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	459.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.921 MAX_MED: 0.417 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Aspartame
 CHID: 20107 CASRN: 22839-47-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K12
 M4ID: 30007638

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	539.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.196 MAX_MED: 0.265 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Aspirin

CHID: 20108 CASRN: 50-78-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D13

M4ID: 30008195

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.43 MAX_MED: -0.325 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Atrazine

CHID: 20112 CASRN: 1912-24-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N11

M4ID: 30007709

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	525.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.14 MAX_MED: 2.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Auramine hydrochloride
CHID: 20114 CASRN: 2465-27-2
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J09
M4ID: 30008029

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	601.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.41 MAX_MED: 9.23 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium azide

CHID: 20121 CASRN: 26628-22-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D11

M4ID: 30007719

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	487.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.279 MAX_MED: 1.14 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Azinphos-methyl

CHID: 20122 CASRN: 86-50-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B19

M4ID: 30008237

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	550.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.04 MAX_MED: 4.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3'-Azido-3'-deoxythymidine

CHID: 20127 CASRN: 30516-87-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L14

M4ID: 30007664

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	451.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.66 MAX_MED: 3.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benzidine

CHID: 20137 CASRN: 92-87-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G13

M4ID: 30008097

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	495.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.3 MAX_MED: 4.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium benzoate

CHID: 20140 CASRN: 532-32-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K11

M4ID: 30008003

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	537.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.41 MAX_MED: -1.19 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,3-Benzofuran

CHID: 20141 CASRN: 271-89-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D21

M4ID: 30007997

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	368.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.07 MAX_MED: 0.836 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benzoic acid

CHID: 20143 CASRN: 65-85-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G12

M4ID: 30008098

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	531.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.8 MAX_MED: -1.71 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,2,3-Benzotriazole

CHID: 20147 CASRN: 95-14-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N21

M4ID: 30007849

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	380.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.831 MAX_MED: 0.625 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benzyl acetate

CHID: 20151 CASRN: 140-11-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D23

M4ID: 30008185

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	397.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.31 MAX_MED: 1.83 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benzyl alcohol

CHID: 20152 CASRN: 100-51-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N07

M4ID: 30007863

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	498.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.9 MAX_MED: -2.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Bis(2-chloroethyl) ether

CHID: 20168 CASRN: 111-44-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K03

M4ID: 30008011

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	452.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.34 MAX_MED: 1.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Methyl-2-tert-butylphenol

CHID: 20212 CASRN: 2409-55-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078002

M4ID: 30007844

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	639.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.56 MAX_MED: 3.85 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Butyrolactone

CHID: 20224 CASRN: 96-48-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N12

M4ID: 30007710

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	579.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.194 MAX_MED: 1.42 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Caffeine

CHID: 20232 CASRN: 58-08-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K18

M4ID: 30007924

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	524.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.59 MAX_MED: -1.32 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Chloro-4-nitrobenzene

CHID: 20281 CASRN: 100-00-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B05

M4ID: 30008251

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	462.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.521 MAX_MED: 0.674 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Chloro-4-methylaniline

CHID: 20286 CASRN: 95-74-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F09

M4ID: 30008151

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	417.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.91 MAX_MED: 2.55 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Chloroaniline

CHID: 20295 CASRN: 106-47-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H15

M4ID: 30007569

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	420.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.42 MAX_MED: 1.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Monuron

CHID: 20311 CASRN: 150-68-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J12

M4ID: 30008026

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	535.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.28 MAX_MED: -0.428 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Citric acid

CHID: 20332 CASRN: 77-92-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H23

M4ID: 30008063

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	373.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.66 MAX_MED: 2.47 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Coumaphos

CHID: 20347 CASRN: 56-72-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K21

M4ID: 30007647

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	429.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.45 MAX_MED: 0.595 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-5-methylaniline

CHID: 20350 CASRN: 120-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E10

M4ID: 30007984

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	445.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.76 MAX_MED: 2.72 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cyclohexanone

CHID: 20359 CASRN: 108-94-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I17

M4ID: 30008045

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	450.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.41 MAX_MED: 2.43 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene
 CHID: 20409 CASRN: 53-70-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H04
 M4ID: 30008082

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	551.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.05 MAX_MED: 4.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Propyzamide

CHID: 20420 CASRN: 23950-58-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K12

M4ID: 30008002

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	528.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.856 MAX_MED: 1.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dichlone

CHID: 20425 CASRN: 117-80-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E09

M4ID: 30008175

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	517.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.34 MAX_MED: 6.81 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,4-Dichlorobenzene

CHID: 20431 CASRN: 106-46-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091014

M4ID: 30008113

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	468.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.32 MAX_MED: 4.81 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dichlorprop

CHID: 20440 CASRN: 120-36-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B13

M4ID: 30008243

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	469.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.17 MAX_MED: -1.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dichlorvos

CHID: 20449 CASRN: 62-73-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D14

M4ID: 30007716

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	429.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.53 MAX_MED: 1.83 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethyl hydrogen phosphite

CHID: 20493 CASRN: 868-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J19

M4ID: 30007621

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	467.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.653 MAX_MED: 0.074 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethyl methylphosphonate

CHID: 20494 CASRN: 756-79-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M20

M4ID: 30007694

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	486.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.4 MAX_MED: -1.55 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethylaminoethanol
 CHID: 20505 CASRN: 108-01-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H24
 M4ID: 30007578

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	417.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.934 MAX_MED: 1.23 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N,N-Dimethylaniline

CHID: 20507 CASRN: 121-69-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E08

M4ID: 30008176

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	592.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.79 MAX_MED: -2.85 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,1-Dimethylhydrazine
 CHID: 20516 CASRN: 57-14-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H06
 M4ID: 30008080

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	509.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.6 MAX_MED: 4.22 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,4-Dinitrotoluene

CHID: 20529 CASRN: 121-14-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L02

M4ID: 30007652

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	372.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.715 MAX_MED: 0.854 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium erythorbate (1:1)

CHID: 20570 CASRN: 6381-77-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H14

M4ID: 30007568

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	460.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.79 MAX_MED: 4.07 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethylene glycol

CHID: 20597 CASRN: 107-21-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D22

M4ID: 30008186

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	517.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0922 MAX_MED: 0.869 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Vinyl-1-cyclohexene dioxide

CHID: 20604 CASRN: 106-87-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078006

M4ID: 30007840

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	535.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.4 MAX_MED: -1.39 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Ethyl-1-hexanol

CHID: 20605 CASRN: 104-76-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078021

M4ID: 30007825

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	373.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.12 MAX_MED: 0.936 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Eugenol

CHID: 20617 CASRN: 97-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K17

M4ID: 30007925

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	501.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.55 MAX_MED: 6.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Finasteride

CHID: 20625 CASRN: 98319-26-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D22

M4ID: 30007996

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	405.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.982 MAX_MED: 0.643 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fluometuron

CHID: 20628 CASRN: 2164-17-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078012

M4ID: 30007834

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	524.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.103 MAX_MED: 0.28 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 5-Fluorouracil

CHID: 20634 CASRN: 51-21-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I02

M4ID: 30007580

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	383.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.249 MAX_MED: -0.183 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Glycidol

CHID: 20666 CASRN: 556-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N20

M4ID: 30007850

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	496.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.19 MAX_MED: -0.783 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: FD&C Green No. 3

CHID: 20673 CASRN: 2353-45-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N22

M4ID: 30007848

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	423.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.19 MAX_MED: 2.65 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Hexachloro-1,3-butadiene

CHID: 20683 CASRN: 87-68-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I18

M4ID: 30008044

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	513.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.419 MAX_MED: 0.369 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: beta-Hexachlorocyclohexane

CHID: 20685 CASRN: 319-85-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H10

M4ID: 30007564

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	622.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.65	MAX_MED:	5.73	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Hexachlorocyclopentadiene

CHID: 20688 CASRN: 77-47-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F06

M4ID: 30007964

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	386.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.29 MAX_MED: 2.72 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methenamine

CHID: 20692 CASRN: 100-97-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G08

M4ID: 30007938

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	396.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.33 MAX_MED: 1.79 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 8-Hydroxyquinoline

CHID: 20730 CASRN: 148-24-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N06

M4ID: 30007704

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	606.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.6 MAX_MED: 8.99 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isophorone

CHID: 20759 CASRN: 78-59-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L05

M4ID: 30007913

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	506.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.86 MAX_MED: 3.04 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Maleic hydrazide

CHID: 20792 CASRN: 123-33-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C04

M4ID: 30007750

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	519.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.57 MAX_MED: -1.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: dL-Menthol

CHID: 20805 CASRN: 89-78-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I14

M4ID: 30008048

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	434.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.61 MAX_MED: 1.71 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methyl carbamate

CHID: 20834 CASRN: 598-55-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A22

M4ID: 30008309

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	608.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.84 MAX_MED: -2.14 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methyl methanesulfonate

CHID: 20845 CASRN: 66-27-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N15

M4ID: 30008136

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	423.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.25 MAX_MED: 1.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone
 CHID: 20856 CASRN: 872-50-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A23
 M4ID: 30008257

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	548.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.631 MAX_MED: 0.696 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 6-Methylquinoline

CHID: 20887 CASRN: 91-62-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C06

M4ID: 30008226

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	520.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.915 MAX_MED: 0.805 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 6-Methyl-2-thiouracil

CHID: 20890 CASRN: 56-04-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F19

M4ID: 30008141

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.04 MAX_MED: 1.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Busulfan

CHID: 20910 CASRN: 55-98-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P15

M4ID: 30007775

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	488.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.859 MAX_MED: -0.677 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Naphthalene

CHID: 20913 CASRN: 91-20-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M02

M4ID: 30007676

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	389.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.377 MAX_MED: 0.0743 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Naphthaleneacetic acid

CHID: 20915 CASRN: 86-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F05

M4ID: 30007965

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	382.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.78 MAX_MED: 2.49 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Naphthylamine

CHID: 20921 CASRN: 91-59-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G06

M4ID: 30008104

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	533.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.59	MAX_MED: 5.03	BMAD: 3.31
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COFF: 9.93	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Nicotine

CHID: 20930 CASRN: 54-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D07

M4ID: 30008201

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	492.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.16 MAX_MED: 2.78 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Nicotinic acid

CHID: 20932 CASRN: 59-67-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J10

M4ID: 30008028

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	461.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.77 MAX_MED: 2.02 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-5-nitroaniline

CHID: 20943 CASRN: 99-59-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I11

M4ID: 30008051

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	519.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.9 MAX_MED: -1.83 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Nitrofurazone

CHID: 20944 CASRN: 59-87-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078005

M4ID: 30007841

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	531.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.83 MAX_MED: 3.47 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Methyl-5-nitroaniline

CHID: 20959 CASRN: 99-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G18

M4ID: 30007928

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	437.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.967 MAX_MED: 1.16 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Nitrobenzene

CHID: 20964 CASRN: 98-95-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E23

M4ID: 30007971

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	379.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.925 MAX_MED: 0.665 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Nitrobenzoic acid
 CHID: 20966 CASRN: 62-23-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I03
 M4ID: 30007581

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	511.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.87 MAX_MED: 1.38 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Nitrofen

CHID: 20970 CASRN: 1836-75-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N22

M4ID: 30008129

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	417.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.59 MAX_MED: 1.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N-Nitrosodimethylamine

CHID: 21029 CASRN: 62-75-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P13

M4ID: 30007809

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	435.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.27 MAX_MED: 1.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N-Nitrosodipropylamine
 CHID: 21032 CASRN: 621-64-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J14
 M4ID: 30007616

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	421.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.86 MAX_MED: 3.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Oxazepam

CHID: 21087 CASRN: 604-75-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A15

M4ID: 30008265

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	606.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -4.03 MAX_MED: -3.24 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Oxydianiline

CHID: 21094 CASRN: 101-80-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G10

M4ID: 30008100

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	515.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.16 MAX_MED: 2.55 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Oxytetracycline hydrochloride

CHID: 21097 CASRN: 2058-46-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P02

M4ID: 30007762

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	434.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.04 MAX_MED: 2.11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Phenylmercuric acetate
 CHID: 21150 CASRN: 62-38-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E09
 M4ID: 30007985

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	608.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.74 MAX_MED: 5.85 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Phenylphenol

CHID: 21151 CASRN: 90-43-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N03

M4ID: 30007701

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	531.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.02 MAX_MED: 5.27 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Prednisone
 CHID: 21185 CASRN: 53-03-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I05
 M4ID: 30008057

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	458.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.41 MAX_MED: 2.23 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Propazine

CHID: 21196 CASRN: 139-40-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E18

M4ID: 30007976 BRK

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	554.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.516	MAX_MED:	-0.184	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pebulate

CHID: 21199 CASRN: 1114-71-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H11

M4ID: 30008075

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	441.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.71	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.532 MAX_MED: 0.702 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 6-Propyl-2-thiouracil

CHID: 21209 CASRN: 51-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A20

M4ID: 30008260

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	644.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -4.79 MAX_MED: -3.89 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Retinol acetate

CHID: 21240 CASRN: 127-47-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G05

M4ID: 30008105

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	496.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.69 MAX_MED: 3.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Rifampicin

CHID: 21244 CASRN: 13292-46-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P17

M4ID: 30007777

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	516.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.289 MAX_MED: -0.319 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sulfasalazine

CHID: 21256 CASRN: 599-79-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M05

M4ID: 30007889

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	504.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.81 MAX_MED: -0.88 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium chlorite

CHID: 21272 CASRN: 7758-19-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J11

M4ID: 30008027

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	514.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.59 MAX_MED: -1.71 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2E,4E-Hexadienoic acid

CHID: 21277 CASRN: 110-44-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K24

M4ID: 30007918

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	440.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.722 MAX_MED: 1.07 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Disulfiram

CHID: 21322 CASRN: 97-77-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G21

M4ID: 30008089

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	559.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.25 MAX_MED: 5.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Thiourea

CHID: 21348 CASRN: 62-56-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L17

M4ID: 30007667

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	494.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.26 MAX_MED: -0.995 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: dl-alpha-Tocopheryl acetate

CHID: 21356 CASRN: 52225-20-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D08

M4ID: 30008200

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	578.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.29 MAX_MED: -1.87 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,4,6-Trichlorophenol

CHID: 21386 CASRN: 88-06-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F06

M4ID: 30008154

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	549.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.1 MAX_MED: 1.48 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Triethylene glycol

CHID: 21393 CASRN: 112-27-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078017

M4ID: 30007829

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	449.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.74	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.812 MAX_MED: 1.38 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Trifluralin

CHID: 21395 CASRN: 1582-09-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B08

M4ID: 30008299

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	517.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.643 MAX_MED: 0.553 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Trimethyl phosphate
 CHID: 21403 CASRN: 512-56-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F18
 M4ID: 30007952

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	475.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.645 MAX_MED: 1.06 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Triphenyltin hydroxide

CHID: 21409 CASRN: 76-87-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I21

M4ID: 30008041

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	574.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.52	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.74 MAX_MED: 8.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Urethane
 CHID: 21427 CASRN: 51-79-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M11
 M4ID: 30007685

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	495.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.67 MAX_MED: 2.58 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: FD&C Yellow 5

CHID: 21455 CASRN: 1934-21-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C18

M4ID: 30007736

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	441.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.154 MAX_MED: -0.352 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ziram
 CHID: 21464 CASRN: 137-30-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A08
 M4ID: 30008272

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	622.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.71 MAX_MED: 2.89 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fumaric acid

CHID: 21518 CASRN: 110-17-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P23

M4ID: 30007799

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	502.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00134 MAX_MED: -0.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethanol

CHID: 21519 CASRN: 112-34-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N17

M4ID: 30007853

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	483.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.675 MAX_MED: -0.293 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 21520 CASRN: 143-22-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F16

M4ID: 30008144

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	556.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.53 MAX_MED: -1.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Decanal

CHID: 21553 CASRN: 112-31-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E24

M4ID: 30008160

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	469.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.47 MAX_MED: 2.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Decanoic acid

CHID: 21554 CASRN: 334-48-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D21

M4ID: 30008187

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	494.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.65 MAX_MED: 2.82 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dalapon

CHID: 21575 CASRN: 75-99-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P22

M4ID: 30007800

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	568.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.92 MAX_MED: -2.02 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Heptanoic acid

CHID: 21600 CASRN: 111-14-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P03

M4ID: 30007763

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	511.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.9	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.57 MAX_MED: 1.78 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Hexanoic acid

CHID: 21607 CASRN: 142-62-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N06

M4ID: 30007864

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	508.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.883 MAX_MED: -1.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Nonanoic acid

CHID: 21641 CASRN: 112-05-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M21

M4ID: 30007873

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	425.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.86 MAX_MED: 3.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Octadecanoic acid

CHID: 21642 CASRN: 57-11-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K07

M4ID: 30007633

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	455.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.615 MAX_MED: 0.741 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tetradecanoic acid

CHID: 21666 CASRN: 544-63-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L23

M4ID: 30007895

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	435.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.79 MAX_MED: 1.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Propanol

CHID: 21739 CASRN: 71-23-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N24

M4ID: 30007846

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	455.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.128 MAX_MED: 0.312 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 5,5-Dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 21754 CASRN: 77-71-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J07

M4ID: 30008031

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	541.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.12 MAX_MED: -2.36 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate

CHID: 21758 CASRN: 78-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078022

M4ID: 30007824

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	501.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.56 MAX_MED: 2.28 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Trifluoromethyl-4-nitrophenol

CHID: 21788 CASRN: 88-30-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091023

M4ID: 30007759

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	451.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.46 MAX_MED: 3.29 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Naphthol

CHID: 21793 CASRN: 90-15-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F01

M4ID: 30007969

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	478.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.94 MAX_MED: 5.87 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Quinoline

CHID: 21798 CASRN: 91-22-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I10

M4ID: 30007588

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	554.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.252 MAX_MED: 0.422 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N,N-Diethylaniline

CHID: 21800 CASRN: 91-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N02

M4ID: 30007700

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	394.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.718 MAX_MED: 0.329 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: o-Cresol
 CHID: 21808 CASRN: 95-48-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N23
 M4ID: 30007847

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	460.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0947 MAX_MED: 0.131 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3,4-Dichloroaniline

CHID: 21815 CASRN: 95-76-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L22

M4ID: 30007672

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	405.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.294 MAX_MED: -0.374 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Butanone oxime

CHID: 21821 CASRN: 96-29-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H21

M4ID: 30007575

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	378.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.654 MAX_MED: 0.467 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Acetophenone

CHID: 21828 CASRN: 98-86-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H08

M4ID: 30008078

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	540.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2 MAX_MED: -1.61 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Nitrotoluene

CHID: 21831 CASRN: 99-08-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B16

M4ID: 30008291

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.59 MAX_MED: 2.67 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N,N,4-Trimethylaniline

CHID: 21832 CASRN: 99-97-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078018

M4ID: 30007828

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	467.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.156 MAX_MED: -0.204 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cyclohexanone oxime

CHID: 21842 CASRN: 100-64-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M10

M4ID: 30007684

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	538.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.16 MAX_MED: 1.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N-Ethyl-3-methylaniline

CHID: 21848 CASRN: 102-27-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N18

M4ID: 30007852

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	479.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.02 MAX_MED: 3.17 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diethyl propanedioate

CHID: 21863 CASRN: 105-53-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F20

M4ID: 30007950

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	483.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.984 MAX_MED: -0.747 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,4-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 21864 CASRN: 105-67-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M08

M4ID: 30007682

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	449.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.37 MAX_MED: 2.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: p-Cresol
 CHID: 21869 CASRN: 106-44-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A07
 M4ID: 30008273

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	538.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.414 MAX_MED: -0.373 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Pentanone

CHID: 21888 CASRN: 107-87-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P12

M4ID: 30007772

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	639.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.6	MAX_MED:	-0.0513	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cyclohexanol

CHID: 21894 CASRN: 108-93-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F17

M4ID: 30008143

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	418.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.375 MAX_MED: 0.345 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Propanedinitrile

CHID: 21907 CASRN: 109-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F19

M4ID: 30007951

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	451.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.791 MAX_MED: -0.358 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 5-Methyl-2-hexanone

CHID: 21914 CASRN: 110-12-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K20

M4ID: 30007646

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	495.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0898 MAX_MED: 0.088 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-(Ethylamino)ethanol
 CHID: 21922 CASRN: 110-73-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G04
 M4ID: 30008106

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	514.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.549 MAX_MED: -0.32 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethylene glycol monoethyl ether acetate

CHID: 21928 CASRN: 111-15-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J20

M4ID: 30008018

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	534.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.19 MAX_MED: -1.83 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Hexanedinitrile
 CHID: 21936 CASRN: 111-69-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M14
 M4ID: 30007688

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	437.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.49 MAX_MED: 3.53 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Octanol

CHID: 21940 CASRN: 111-87-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F21

M4ID: 30008139

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	453.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.843 MAX_MED: 0.774 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethanol

CHID: 21941 CASRN: 111-90-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G18

M4ID: 30008092

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	540.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.5 MAX_MED: -1.78 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Undecanone

CHID: 21943 CASRN: 112-12-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L07

M4ID: 30007911

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	510.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.26 MAX_MED: -1.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Decanol

CHID: 21946 CASRN: 112-30-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I22

M4ID: 30008040

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	445.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.46 MAX_MED: 0.841 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Propoxur

CHID: 21948 CASRN: 114-26-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F08

M4ID: 30007962

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	403.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.437 MAX_MED: 0.573 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde

CHID: 21969 CASRN: 121-33-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M24

M4ID: 30007870

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	553.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.27 MAX_MED: -1.39 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethyl hexanoate

CHID: 21980 CASRN: 123-66-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M03

M4ID: 30007891

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	444.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.08 MAX_MED: 3.18 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tributyl phosphate

CHID: 21986 CASRN: 126-73-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K01

M4ID: 30007627

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	418.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.38 MAX_MED: 4.02 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: DEET
 CHID: 21995 CASRN: 134-62-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A08
 M4ID: 30007790

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	575.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.32 MAX_MED: -2.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethanolamine

CHID: 22000 CASRN: 141-43-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H21

M4ID: 30008065

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	429.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.97 MAX_MED: 1.62 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Nonanol

CHID: 22008 CASRN: 143-08-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M22

M4ID: 30007872

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	424.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.421 MAX_MED: 0.712 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Disulfoton
 CHID: 22018 CASRN: 298-04-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B23
 M4ID: 30008284

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	573.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.169 MAX_MED: 0.189 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Bromacil

CHID: 22020 CASRN: 314-40-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G10

M4ID: 30007936

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	526.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.17 MAX_MED: 3.02 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,3-Dichlorobenzene

CHID: 22056 CASRN: 541-73-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C22

M4ID: 30007732

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.549 MAX_MED: -0.799 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Propanil

CHID: 22111 CASRN: 709-98-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N24

M4ID: 30008127

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	455.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.09 MAX_MED: 2.75 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3,4-Dichloro-1-butene

CHID: 22113 CASRN: 760-23-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H24

M4ID: 30008062

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	425.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.21 MAX_MED: 2.02 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: (Z)-3-Hexen-1-ol

CHID: 22137 CASRN: 928-96-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M18

M4ID: 30007876

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	487.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.664 MAX_MED: -0.121 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Bromoxynil

CHID: 22162 CASRN: 1689-84-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E21

M4ID: 30007973

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	428.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.45 MAX_MED: 1.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: EPN

CHID: 22174 CASRN: 2104-64-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078010

M4ID: 30007836

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	543.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.82 MAX_MED: 8.22 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,3,6-Trimethylphenol

CHID: 22187 CASRN: 2416-94-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G11

M4ID: 30008099

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	485.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.05 MAX_MED: 0.242 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-(Butan-2-yl)phenol

CHID: 22331 CASRN: 89-72-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K15

M4ID: 30007641

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	453.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.949 MAX_MED: 0.715 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Phenol red

CHID: 22408 CASRN: 143-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A06

M4ID: 30007792

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	512.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.35 MAX_MED: -2.32 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Methylenebis(2,6-di-t-butylphenol)

CHID: 22411 CASRN: 118-82-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I02

M4ID: 30008060

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	544.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.02 MAX_MED: 2.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Melatonin
 CHID: 22421 CASRN: 73-31-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E07
 M4ID: 30008177

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	475.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.05 MAX_MED: 2.32 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Butylbenzene

CHID: 22472 CASRN: 104-51-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C21

M4ID: 30007733

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	395.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.718 MAX_MED: 0.565 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Corticosterone

CHID: 22474 CASRN: 50-22-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091005

M4ID: 30008122

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	512.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.835 MAX_MED: 0.889 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: E-Cinnamic acid

CHID: 22489 CASRN: 140-10-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B01

M4ID: 30008255

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	671.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.278 MAX_MED: -0.77 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Digoxin

CHID: 22934 CASRN: 20830-75-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F14

M4ID: 30008146

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	629.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.71 MAX_MED: 9.15 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Lactose

CHID: 23193 CASRN: 63-42-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M01

M4ID: 30007893

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	628.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.31 MAX_MED: 4.21 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Letrozole

CHID: 23202 CASRN: 112809-51-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K22

M4ID: 30007648

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	436.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.901 MAX_MED: -1.21 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Mifepristone

CHID: 23322 CASRN: 84371-65-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B01

M4ID: 30008306

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	521.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.88	MAX_MED:	3.69	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pentaerythritol tetranitrate

CHID: 23430 CASRN: 78-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F02

M4ID: 30007968

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	537.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.24 MAX_MED: -1.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pyridoxine

CHID: 23541 CASRN: 65-23-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G01

M4ID: 30007945

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	376.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.595 MAX_MED: 1.48 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Retinol

CHID: 23556 CASRN: 68-26-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H14

M4ID: 30008072

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	459.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.754 MAX_MED: 0.725 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Butanedioic acid

CHID: 23602 CASRN: 110-15-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I07

M4ID: 30007585

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	458.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.171 MAX_MED: 1.28 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tetracycline

CHID: 23645 CASRN: 60-54-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C11

M4ID: 30008221

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	493.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.414 MAX_MED: 0.605 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 6-Thioguanine

CHID: 23652 CASRN: 154-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E05

M4ID: 30008179

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	489.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.17 MAX_MED: 3.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Warfarin

CHID: 23742 CASRN: 81-81-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B07

M4ID: 30008249

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	519.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.938 MAX_MED: -0.349 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: D-Xylose

CHID: 23745 CASRN: 58-86-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J12

M4ID: 30007614

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	510.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.83	MAX_MED:	1.52	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Nitrotoluene

CHID: 23792 CASRN: 99-99-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D06

M4ID: 30008202

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	504.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.1 MAX_MED: -1.38 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isophorone diisocyanate

CHID: 23826 CASRN: 4098-71-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B08

M4ID: 30008248

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	563.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.311 MAX_MED: -0.707 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Acenaphthylene

CHID: 23845 CASRN: 208-96-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A06

M4ID: 30008274

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	658.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -4.7 MAX_MED: -4.41 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Acephate

CHID: 23846 CASRN: 30560-19-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C19

M4ID: 30008213

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	533.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.27 MAX_MED: -1.39 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Acetochlor

CHID: 23848 CASRN: 34256-82-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E24

M4ID: 30007970

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	449.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.22 MAX_MED: 2.45 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Aldoxycarb

CHID: 23862 CASRN: 1646-88-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078001

M4ID: 30007845

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	629.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.76 MAX_MED: 3.67 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Amitraz

CHID: 23871 CASRN: 33089-61-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D08

M4ID: 30007722

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	455.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.9 MAX_MED: 3.14 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Anisidine

CHID: 23877 CASRN: 90-04-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I10

M4ID: 30008052

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	473.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.47 MAX_MED: 3.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Clofentezine

CHID: 23881 CASRN: 74115-24-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M05

M4ID: 30007679

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	448.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.04 MAX_MED: 3.24 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Asulam

CHID: 23890 CASRN: 3337-71-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F10

M4ID: 30008150

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	452.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.72 MAX_MED: 1.49 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benfluralin

CHID: 23899 CASRN: 1861-40-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L04

M4ID: 30007654

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.731 MAX_MED: 0.694 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Bentazone

CHID: 23901 CASRN: 25057-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F04

M4ID: 30007966

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	428.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.52	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.943 MAX_MED: 0.844 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benzo(b)fluoranthene

CHID: 23907 CASRN: 205-99-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I23

M4ID: 30007601

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	333.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.255 MAX_MED: 0.389 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Butylate

CHID: 23936 CASRN: 2008-41-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B05

M4ID: 30008302

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	441.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.908 MAX_MED: 0.933 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Carbosulfan

CHID: 23950 CASRN: 55285-14-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A15

M4ID: 30008316

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	570.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.07 MAX_MED: -1.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Carboxin

CHID: 23951 CASRN: 5234-68-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C16

M4ID: 30007738

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	478.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.44 MAX_MED: 4.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cyclohexylamine

CHID: 23996 CASRN: 108-91-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F08

M4ID: 30008152

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	558.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.41 MAX_MED: -2.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cypermethrin

CHID: 23998 CASRN: 52315-07-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N09

M4ID: 30007861

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	591.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.21 MAX_MED: 7.51 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cyromazine

CHID: 23999 CASRN: 66215-27-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091007

M4ID: 30008120

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	457.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.52 MAX_MED: 1.16 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dicamba

CHID: 24018 CASRN: 1918-00-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A10

M4ID: 30007788

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	588.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.35 MAX_MED: -3.42 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diethyl sulfate

CHID: 24045 CASRN: 64-67-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M20

M4ID: 30007874

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	534.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.66 MAX_MED: -0.866 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diisopropyl methylphosphonate

CHID: 24051 CASRN: 1445-75-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091015

M4ID: 30008112

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	431.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.69 MAX_MED: 2.11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethipin

CHID: 24052 CASRN: 55290-64-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K13

M4ID: 30008001

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	473.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.76 MAX_MED: 7.44 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethyl sulfate

CHID: 24055 CASRN: 77-78-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D03

M4ID: 30007727

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	377.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.862 MAX_MED: 1.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethylamine

CHID: 24057 CASRN: 124-40-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J05

M4ID: 30007607

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	443.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.94 MAX_MED: 2.53 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3,3'-Dimethylbenzidine
 CHID: 24059 CASRN: 119-93-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G09
 M4ID: 30007937

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	582.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.25 MAX_MED: 6.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3,4-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 24062 CASRN: 95-65-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E15

M4ID: 30007979

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	452.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.89 MAX_MED: 3.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,6-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 24063 CASRN: 576-26-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A19

M4ID: 30008261

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	599.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.37 MAX_MED: -1.57 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,3-Dinitrobenzene

CHID: 24065 CASRN: 99-65-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N14

M4ID: 30008137

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	517.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.55 MAX_MED: 6.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diphenamid

CHID: 24072 CASRN: 957-51-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B12

M4ID: 30008295

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	415.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.38 MAX_MED: 3.21 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethion
 CHID: 24086 CASRN: 563-12-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E19
 M4ID: 30008165

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	588.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.07 MAX_MED: 4.26 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Butoxyethanol
 CHID: 24097 CASRN: 111-76-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M12
 M4ID: 30007882

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	516.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.62 MAX_MED: -1.26 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fenamiphos

CHID: 24102 CASRN: 22224-92-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C08

M4ID: 30007746

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	442.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.77 MAX_MED: 4.92 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Flutolanil

CHID: 24109 CASRN: 66332-96-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G17

M4ID: 30007929

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	486.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.39 MAX_MED: 3.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fomesafen

CHID: 24112 CASRN: 72178-02-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A16

M4ID: 30008315

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	538.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.5 MAX_MED: -0.221 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isopropalin
 CHID: 24157 CASRN: 33820-53-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N12
 M4ID: 30007858

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	571.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.04 MAX_MED: 7.19 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Lactofen

CHID: 24160 CASRN: 77501-63-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I01

M4ID: 30007579

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	535.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.44 MAX_MED: -1.07 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methacrylonitrile

CHID: 24176 CASRN: 126-98-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C20

M4ID: 30007734

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	497.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.413 MAX_MED: -0.124 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methamidophos

CHID: 24177 CASRN: 10265-92-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A04

M4ID: 30007794

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	593.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.13 MAX_MED: -3.27 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: MCPB

CHID: 24193 CASRN: 94-81-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K13

M4ID: 30007639

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	443.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.91 MAX_MED: 4.05 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Mecoprop

CHID: 24194 CASRN: 93-65-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P03

M4ID: 30007819

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	507.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.172 MAX_MED: -0.065 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: m-Cresol

CHID: 24200 CASRN: 108-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I19

M4ID: 30007597

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	467.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.635 MAX_MED: 0.252 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Nitrapyrin

CHID: 24216 CASRN: 1929-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G04

M4ID: 30007942

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	439.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.71	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.565 MAX_MED: 0.851 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Oxyfluorfen
 CHID: 24241 CASRN: 42874-03-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L08
 M4ID: 30007658

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	500.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.91 MAX_MED: 1.61 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Phosphoric acid

CHID: 24263 CASRN: 7664-38-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K14

M4ID: 30007640

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	480.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.98 MAX_MED: 4.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Prometryn

CHID: 24272 CASRN: 7287-19-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G16

M4ID: 30007930

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	473.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.11 MAX_MED: 2.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Propargite

CHID: 24276 CASRN: 2312-35-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D06

M4ID: 30007724

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	561.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.15 MAX_MED: 6.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pyrene

CHID: 24289 CASRN: 129-00-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M23

M4ID: 30007697

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	416.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.89 MAX_MED: 2.07 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Hexythiazox

CHID: 24299 CASRN: 78587-05-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I24

M4ID: 30007602

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	400.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.44 MAX_MED: 2.67 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sethoxydim

CHID: 24304 CASRN: 74051-80-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D09

M4ID: 30007721

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	445.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.07 MAX_MED: 1.71 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium fluoroacetate

CHID: 24311 CASRN: 62-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N13

M4ID: 30007857

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	460.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.1 MAX_MED: 3.07 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Myclobutanil

CHID: 24315 CASRN: 88671-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G24

M4ID: 30008086

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	499.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.04 MAX_MED: 5.26 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tebuthiuron

CHID: 24316 CASRN: 34014-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M04

M4ID: 30007678

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	456.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3 MAX_MED: 2.71 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,2,4,5-Tetrachlorobenzene

CHID: 24320 CASRN: 95-94-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C24

M4ID: 30007730

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	441.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0893 MAX_MED: 0.606 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Thiophanate-methyl

CHID: 24338 CASRN: 23564-05-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I19

M4ID: 30008043

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.1 MAX_MED: 0.483 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tri-allate

CHID: 24344 CASRN: 2303-17-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K16

M4ID: 30007642

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	489.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.1 MAX_MED: 1.65 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,4,5-Trichlorophenol

CHID: 24359 CASRN: 95-95-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J22

M4ID: 30007624

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	440.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.76 MAX_MED: 1.63 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 24368 CASRN: 112-50-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J02

M4ID: 30007604

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	510.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.801 MAX_MED: -1.13 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Acetic acid

CHID: 24394 CASRN: 64-19-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078023

M4ID: 30007823

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	447.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.179 MAX_MED: 0.47 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Aminobenzoic acid

CHID: 24466 CASRN: 150-13-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C13

M4ID: 30008219

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0154 MAX_MED: -0.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 5-Amino-2-methylphenol

CHID: 24489 CASRN: 2835-95-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N10

M4ID: 30007860

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	578.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.77 MAX_MED: 5.93 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diethylene glycol dimethyl ether

CHID: 24621 CASRN: 111-96-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G03

M4ID: 30008107

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	428.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.93 MAX_MED: 2.06 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Bromo-1-propanol

CHID: 24657 CASRN: 627-18-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E05

M4ID: 30007989

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	348.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.83 MAX_MED: 1.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: tert-Butylamine

CHID: 24681 CASRN: 75-64-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P18

M4ID: 30007778

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	551.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.78 MAX_MED: -1.68 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: D-Camphor

CHID: 24721 CASRN: 464-49-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G14

M4ID: 30008096

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	496.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.827 MAX_MED: 0.281 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Carbendazim

CHID: 24729 CASRN: 10605-21-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P06

M4ID: 30007766

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.6 MAX_MED: 1.95 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Colchicine

CHID: 24845 CASRN: 64-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J06

M4ID: 30007608

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	562.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.53 MAX_MED: 5.19 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cycloheximide

CHID: 24882 CASRN: 66-81-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D09

M4ID: 30008199

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	609.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.75	MAX_MED: 8.01	BMAD: 3.31
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COFF: 9.93	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,6-Hexanediamine

CHID: 24922 CASRN: 124-09-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L20

M4ID: 30007670

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	474.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.58 MAX_MED: -1.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3,4-Diaminotoluene

CHID: 24930 CASRN: 496-72-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M03

M4ID: 30007677

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	508.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.42 MAX_MED: 6.96 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Di-tert-butyl peroxide
 CHID: 24955 CASRN: 110-05-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F23
 M4ID: 30007947

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	361.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.39 MAX_MED: 1.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Dichlorodiphenyl sulfone

CHID: 24986 CASRN: 80-07-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B22

M4ID: 30008285

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	501.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.76 MAX_MED: 1.97 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benzal chloride

CHID: 25014 CASRN: 98-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D05

M4ID: 30007725

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	376.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0816 MAX_MED: 0.235 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diethylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 25049 CASRN: 111-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I24

M4ID: 30008038

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	412.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.72 MAX_MED: 2.18 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diethylenetriamine

CHID: 25050 CASRN: 111-40-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N03

M4ID: 30007867

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	453.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.31 MAX_MED: 1.05 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dihexyl phthalate

CHID: 25068 CASRN: 84-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H12

M4ID: 30008074

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	605.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.31 MAX_MED: -3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diisobutyl ketone

CHID: 25080 CASRN: 108-83-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D12

M4ID: 30008196

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	537.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.52	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.05 MAX_MED: -1.57 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethyl adipate

CHID: 25096 CASRN: 627-93-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K16

M4ID: 30007926

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	595.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -4.19 MAX_MED: -3.93 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-(Dimethylamino)propylamine

CHID: 25102 CASRN: 109-55-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K01

M4ID: 30008013

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	701.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.75 MAX_MED: 1.41 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethyl glutarate

CHID: 25122 CASRN: 1119-40-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J22

M4ID: 30008016

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	415.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.05 MAX_MED: 1.24 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,2-Dimethyl-3-nitrobenzene

CHID: 25132 CASRN: 83-41-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L01

M4ID: 30007651

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	384.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0981 MAX_MED: -0.186 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,3-Dimethylolurea

CHID: 25141 CASRN: 140-95-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M12

M4ID: 30007686

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	567.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.326	MAX_MED:	0.565	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Divinylbenzene

CHID: 25216 CASRN: 1321-74-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K04

M4ID: 30008010

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	471.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.72 MAX_MED: 1.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: (2-Dodecenyl)succinic anhydride

CHID: 25217 CASRN: 19780-11-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J02

M4ID: 30008036

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	593.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.58 MAX_MED: 1.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexanoic acid

CHID: 25293 CASRN: 149-57-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L12

M4ID: 30007906

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	533.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.29 MAX_MED: -1.92 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate

CHID: 25300 CASRN: 1241-94-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G17

M4ID: 30008093

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	544.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.47 MAX_MED: 6.79 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 5-Ethylidene-2-norbornene

CHID: 25306 CASRN: 16219-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H22

M4ID: 30007576

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	423.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.487 MAX_MED: -0.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Formamide

CHID: 25337 CASRN: 75-12-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K20

M4ID: 30007922

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	519.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.73 MAX_MED: -1.81 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Hexamethyldisilazane

CHID: 25395 CASRN: 999-97-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N23

M4ID: 30008128

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	380.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.88 MAX_MED: 2.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Hydroxy-2-methylpropanenitrile

CHID: 25427 CASRN: 75-86-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G20

M4ID: 30007550

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	478.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.39 MAX_MED: -1.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Hydroxyurea

CHID: 25438 CASRN: 127-07-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F24

M4ID: 30007946

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	378.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.294 MAX_MED: 0.093 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Methylbutyl acetate

CHID: 25453 CASRN: 123-92-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M17

M4ID: 30007877

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	434.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.924 MAX_MED: 1.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isopentyl alcohol

CHID: 25469 CASRN: 123-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N19

M4ID: 30007851

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	501.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.55 MAX_MED: -2.58 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isopropyl acetate
 CHID: 25478 CASRN: 108-21-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P20
 M4ID: 30007802

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	609.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.43 MAX_MED: -4.49 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isoproterenol hydrochloride

CHID: 25486 CASRN: 51-30-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H10

M4ID: 30008076

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	505.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.16 MAX_MED: 5.85 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Linalool

CHID: 25502 CASRN: 78-70-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G23

M4ID: 30008087

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	396.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.55 MAX_MED: 2.17 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Linoleic acid

CHID: 25505 CASRN: 60-33-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C08

M4ID: 30008224

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	614.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-3.54	MAX_MED:	-2.01	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methyl 2-aminobenzoate
 CHID: 25567 CASRN: 134-20-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H04
 M4ID: 30007558

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	480.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.79 MAX_MED: 1.94 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N,N'-Methylenebisacrylamide

CHID: 25595 CASRN: 110-26-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I15

M4ID: 30007593

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	467.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.92 MAX_MED: 2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methylene bis(thiocyanate)

CHID: 25599 CASRN: 6317-18-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M19

M4ID: 30007875

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	491.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.83 MAX_MED: 6.16 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Myrcene

CHID: 25692 CASRN: 123-35-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E16

M4ID: 30007978

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	296.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.85 MAX_MED: 1.87 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,10-Phenanthroline

CHID: 25857 CASRN: 66-71-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H18

M4ID: 30007572

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	514.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.3 MAX_MED: 2.22 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Ethoxyaniline

CHID: 25864 CASRN: 156-43-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A09

M4ID: 30007789

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	602.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.44 MAX_MED: -3.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethyl 3-phenylglycidate

CHID: 25886 CASRN: 121-39-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D01

M4ID: 30008207

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	651.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.68 MAX_MED: 4.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N-Phenyl-1,4-benzenediamine

CHID: 25895 CASRN: 101-54-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I08

M4ID: 30008054

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	538.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0417 MAX_MED: 1.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium dodecyl sulfate
 CHID: 26031 CASRN: 151-21-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H22
 M4ID: 30008064

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	492.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.06 MAX_MED: 4.62 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Terephthalic acid

CHID: 26080 CASRN: 100-21-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B14

M4ID: 30008242

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	531.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.18 MAX_MED: -0.645 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tetrachlorophthalic anhydride

CHID: 26102 CASRN: 117-08-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I03

M4ID: 30008059

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	474.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.44 MAX_MED: 2.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Theobromine

CHID: 26132 CASRN: 83-67-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P14

M4ID: 30007808

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	403.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.93 MAX_MED: 2.68 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tolyltriazole

CHID: 26171 CASRN: 29385-43-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N11

M4ID: 30007859

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	513.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.77 MAX_MED: -0.975 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Triclocarban

CHID: 26214 CASRN: 101-20-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L21

M4ID: 30007671

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	445.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.05 MAX_MED: 2.47 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Triethylene glycol dimethyl ether

CHID: 26224 CASRN: 112-49-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M01

M4ID: 30007675

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	365.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.56 MAX_MED: 1.82 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Trimellitic anhydride

CHID: 26235 CASRN: 552-30-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G16

M4ID: 30008094

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	553.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.1 MAX_MED: -1.92 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Triglycidyl isocyanurate

CHID: 26262 CASRN: 2451-62-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I06

M4ID: 30007584

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	430.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.22 MAX_MED: 3.39 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Camphene

CHID: 26488 CASRN: 79-92-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C23

M4ID: 30008209

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	407.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.899 MAX_MED: 1.25 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,2,3,6-Tetrahydrophthalimide

CHID: 26513 CASRN: 85-40-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M16

M4ID: 30007878

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	561.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.52 MAX_MED: -1.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Phthalimide

CHID: 26514 CASRN: 85-41-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P08

M4ID: 30007768

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.973 MAX_MED: 0.428 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Symclosene
 CHID: 26523 CASRN: 87-90-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I04
 M4ID: 30007582

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	489.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.67 MAX_MED: 2.27 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Tert-Butyl-5-methylphenol

CHID: 26529 CASRN: 88-60-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C05

M4ID: 30007749

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	413.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.61 MAX_MED: 3.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Triethylene glycol bis(2-ethylhexanoate)

CHID: 26564 CASRN: 94-28-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F03

M4ID: 30007967

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	541.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.656 MAX_MED: 0.792 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-tert-Butylcyclohexanol

CHID: 26623 CASRN: 98-52-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B13

M4ID: 30008294

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	455.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.62 MAX_MED: 0.0554 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,3-Diisopropylbenzene

CHID: 26640 CASRN: 99-62-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P19

M4ID: 30007803

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	557.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.1 MAX_MED: -2.83 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,3-Benzenedicarbonyl dichloride

CHID: 26641 CASRN: 99-63-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P07

M4ID: 30007767

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	460.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0247 MAX_MED: -0.288 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: p-Cymene

CHID: 26645 CASRN: 99-87-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L09

M4ID: 30007659

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	531.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.858 MAX_MED: 1.62 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Hydroxybenzoic acid

CHID: 26647 CASRN: 99-96-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L14

M4ID: 30007904

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	378.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.82 MAX_MED: 1.87 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Pyridinecarbonitrile

CHID: 26665 CASRN: 100-54-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B18

M4ID: 30008289

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	494.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.49 MAX_MED: -1.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-(Phenylmethylene)octanal

CHID: 26684 CASRN: 101-86-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J16

M4ID: 30008022

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	628.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.56 MAX_MED: 4.51 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Triacetin

CHID: 26691 CASRN: 102-76-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K22

M4ID: 30007920

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	444.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0474 MAX_MED: 1.22 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexyl acetate

CHID: 26694 CASRN: 103-09-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D03

M4ID: 30008205

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	530.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.192 MAX_MED: -0.876 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Methyl-2-pentanol

CHID: 26781 CASRN: 108-11-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H19

M4ID: 30008067

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	452.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.132 MAX_MED: 0.584 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Methylaniline

CHID: 26792 CASRN: 108-44-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L18

M4ID: 30007900

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	491.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.983 MAX_MED: -1.28 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benzenethiol

CHID: 26811 CASRN: 108-98-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M04

M4ID: 30007890

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	489.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.542 MAX_MED: 0.888 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isopropyl tetradecanoate

CHID: 26838 CASRN: 110-27-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B06

M4ID: 30008250

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	589.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.03 MAX_MED: -2.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methyl decanoate

CHID: 26842 CASRN: 110-42-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P21

M4ID: 30007781

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	458.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.705 MAX_MED: -0.645 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methyl octanoate

CHID: 26864 CASRN: 111-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J21

M4ID: 30007623

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	429.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.82 MAX_MED: -0.564 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Hexamethyleneimine

CHID: 26879 CASRN: 111-49-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M19

M4ID: 30007693

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	468.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.789 MAX_MED: -0.275 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,2-Ethanedioyl diacetate

CHID: 26880 CASRN: 111-55-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N18

M4ID: 30008133

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	466.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.428 MAX_MED: -0.258 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Methoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 26912 CASRN: 112-35-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H17

M4ID: 30008069

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	443.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0939 MAX_MED: -0.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Undecanol

CHID: 26915 CASRN: 112-42-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G15

M4ID: 30007931

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	438.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.73 MAX_MED: 3.02 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tetraethylene glycol

CHID: 26922 CASRN: 112-60-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E17

M4ID: 30008167

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	504.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.01 MAX_MED: 0.885 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pentaerythritol

CHID: 26943 CASRN: 115-77-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M13

M4ID: 30007881

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	412.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.31 MAX_MED: 2.49 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Methoxybenzaldehyde

CHID: 26997 CASRN: 123-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B23

M4ID: 30008233

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	454.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.735 MAX_MED: 0.561 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate

CHID: 27050 CASRN: 128-04-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P10

M4ID: 30007812

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	524.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.96 MAX_MED: 3.82 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium phenolate

CHID: 27072 CASRN: 139-02-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F07

M4ID: 30007963

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	387.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0419 MAX_MED: 0.47 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Bis(2-ethylhexyl) maleate

CHID: 27094 CASRN: 142-16-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L03

M4ID: 30007915

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	504.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.534 MAX_MED: 0.689 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1H-1,2,4-Triazole

CHID: 27131 CASRN: 288-88-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078015

M4ID: 30007831

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	500.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.61 MAX_MED: -1.33 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,3-Cyclopentadiene
 CHID: 27191 CASRN: 542-92-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J20
 M4ID: 30007622

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	477.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.608 MAX_MED: -0.334 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methyl isothiocyanate

CHID: 27204 CASRN: 556-61-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G24

M4ID: 30007554

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	384.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.29 MAX_MED: 1.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane

CHID: 27205 CASRN: 556-67-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G14

M4ID: 30007932

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.19 MAX_MED: 4.44 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,6-Diethylaniline

CHID: 27218 CASRN: 579-66-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091001

M4ID: 30008126

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	431.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.54 MAX_MED: 2.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Pyrrolidinone

CHID: 27246 CASRN: 616-45-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H19

M4ID: 30007573

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	461.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.907 MAX_MED: -0.738 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isopropyl formate

CHID: 27258 CASRN: 625-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F03

M4ID: 30008157

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	440.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.687 MAX_MED: 0.137 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pentyl acetate

CHID: 27263 CASRN: 628-63-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J23

M4ID: 30008015

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	414.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.28 MAX_MED: 2.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Phenyl phosphorus dichloride

CHID: 27282 CASRN: 644-97-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D20

M4ID: 30007998

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	478.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.503 MAX_MED: -0.298 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dibutyltin dichloride

CHID: 27292 CASRN: 683-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H06

M4ID: 30007560

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	629.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.14 MAX_MED: 6.72 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Phenoxy-2-propanol

CHID: 27312 CASRN: 770-35-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H20

M4ID: 30007574

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	452.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.641 MAX_MED: -0.248 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ammonium carbamate

CHID: 27360 CASRN: 1111-78-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N05

M4ID: 30007865

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.333 MAX_MED: -0.336 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diisooctyl adipate
 CHID: 27388 CASRN: 1330-86-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A13
 M4ID: 30008267

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	594.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.76 MAX_MED: -4.04 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Phenolsulfonic acid

CHID: 27390 CASRN: 1333-39-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B07

M4ID: 30008300

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	467.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.174 MAX_MED: -0.421 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N,N-Dimethylacetamide

CHID: 27454 CASRN: 2044-64-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L05

M4ID: 30007655

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	462.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.26 MAX_MED: 4.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Thiocarbazine

CHID: 27461 CASRN: 2231-57-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I20

M4ID: 30007598

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	467.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.264 MAX_MED: 1.07 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-methylphenol

CHID: 27479 CASRN: 2440-22-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F15

M4ID: 30008145

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	586.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.639 MAX_MED: 0.437 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,3-Diaminotoluene
 CHID: 27494 CASRN: 2687-25-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M10
 M4ID: 30007884

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	579.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5 MAX_MED: 5.79 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,4-D sodium salt

CHID: 27496 CASRN: 2702-72-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H18

M4ID: 30008068

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	499.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.836 MAX_MED: 1.48 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Potassium 2-ethylhexanoate

CHID: 27525 CASRN: 3164-85-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G19

M4ID: 30007549

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	452.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.572 MAX_MED: -0.446 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium chloroacetate

CHID: 27550 CASRN: 3926-62-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091020

M4ID: 30007756

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	487.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0839 MAX_MED: 1.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Chlorobenzotrifluoride

CHID: 27593 CASRN: 5216-25-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P01

M4ID: 30007761

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	425.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.1 MAX_MED: 0.893 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Phenoxybenzenemethanol

CHID: 27756 CASRN: 13826-35-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L22

M4ID: 30007896

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	619.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.01 MAX_MED: 0.994 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid

CHID: 27770 CASRN: 15214-89-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L18

M4ID: 30007668

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	466.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1 MAX_MED: -0.386 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dicyclohexyl sodium sulfosuccinate

CHID: 27826 CASRN: 23386-52-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M16

M4ID: 30007690

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	499.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.57 MAX_MED: 1.72 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: tert-Nonanethiol

CHID: 27868 CASRN: 25360-10-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K23

M4ID: 30007649

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	283.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.975 MAX_MED: 1.26 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Calcium dodecylbenzene sulfonate

CHID: 27891 CASRN: 26264-06-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G13

M4ID: 30007933

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	516.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.6	MAX_MED: 4.01	BMAD: 3.31
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COFF: 9.93	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ammonium xylene sulfonate

CHID: 27899 CASRN: 26447-10-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C04

M4ID: 30008228

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	610.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.03 MAX_MED: -0.523 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Neodecanoic acid

CHID: 27916 CASRN: 26896-20-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H07

M4ID: 30007561

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	428.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.77 MAX_MED: 0.551 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diisodecyl hexanedioate

CHID: 27924 CASRN: 27178-16-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B24

M4ID: 30008283

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	548.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.985 MAX_MED: 0.409 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dodecylbenzene sulfonate triethanolamine(1:1)

CHID: 27932 CASRN: 27323-41-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C01

M4ID: 30008282

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	488.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.44 MAX_MED: -0.925 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 27983 CASRN: 34590-94-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F23

M4ID: 30007754

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	353.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.72 MAX_MED: 1.55 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Hexadecanol

CHID: 27991 CASRN: 36653-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H08

M4ID: 30007562

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	310.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.978 MAX_MED: 1.42 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dichlormid

CHID: 27997 CASRN: 37764-25-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D11

M4ID: 30008197

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	471.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.4 MAX_MED: 1.26 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: DINP branched

CHID: 28665 CASRN: 68515-48-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H03

M4ID: 30008083

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	296.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.75 MAX_MED: 2.75 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tetrahydrofurfuryl alcohol

CHID: 29128 CASRN: 97-99-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078004

M4ID: 30007842

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	480.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.43 MAX_MED: 1.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cyclopentanone

CHID: 29154 CASRN: 120-92-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I04

M4ID: 30008058

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	485.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.773 MAX_MED: 0.847 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-(Phenylmethylene)-heptanal

CHID: 29157 CASRN: 122-40-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J24

M4ID: 30008014

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	465.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.03 MAX_MED: -0.253 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,6,8-Trimethyl-4-nonanol

CHID: 29159 CASRN: 123-17-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J15

M4ID: 30008023

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	571.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.482 MAX_MED: -1.48 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Bromo-1-chloro-5,5-dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 29162 CASRN: 126-06-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E07

M4ID: 30007987

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	414.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.63 MAX_MED: 2.09 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Methylpent-3-en-2-one

CHID: 29170 CASRN: 141-79-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A03

M4ID: 30008277

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	603	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.705 MAX_MED: 0.124 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methylionone

CHID: 29214 CASRN: 1335-46-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P17

M4ID: 30007805

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	590.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.9 MAX_MED: -1.85 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Clopyralid

CHID: 29221 CASRN: 1702-17-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D04

M4ID: 30007726

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	519.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.719 MAX_MED: -0.097 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,4-Bis(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)phenol

CHID: 29241 CASRN: 2772-45-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J04

M4ID: 30007606

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	587.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.43 MAX_MED: 6.88 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Triethoxyoctylsilane

CHID: 29246 CASRN: 2943-75-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091008

M4ID: 30008119

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	458.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.9	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.33 MAX_MED: 2.43 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium lauryl polyoxyethylene ether sulfate

CHID: 29298 CASRN: 9004-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J21

M4ID: 30008017

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	546.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 11 MAX_MED: 8.42 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Glyceryl stearate

CHID: 29304 CASRN: 11099-07-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D02

M4ID: 30008206

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	602.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.591 MAX_MED: -0.68 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tripropylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 29329 CASRN: 25498-49-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K04

M4ID: 30007630

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	468.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.08 MAX_MED: 0.835 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diazolidinyl urea

CHID: 29559 CASRN: 78491-02-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J18

M4ID: 30007620

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	461.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.293 MAX_MED: -0.238 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methacrylamide

CHID: 29600 CASRN: 79-39-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J19

M4ID: 30008019

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	487.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.2 MAX_MED: 0.977 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Limonene

CHID: 29612 CASRN: 138-86-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I23

M4ID: 30008039

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	403.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.79 MAX_MED: 3.41 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Thiocyanic acid, ammonium salt

CHID: 29653 CASRN: 1762-95-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M24

M4ID: 30007698

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	405.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.68 MAX_MED: 1.43 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3,5,5-Trimethyl-1-hexanol

CHID: 29661 CASRN: 3452-97-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C23

M4ID: 30007731

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	443.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.302 MAX_MED: 0.0379 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Silica

CHID: 29677 CASRN: 7631-86-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J17

M4ID: 30008021

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	561.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.14 MAX_MED: -0.897 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium persulfate

CHID: 29698 CASRN: 7775-27-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M07

M4ID: 30007681

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	437.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.52 MAX_MED: 2.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,2-Propanediol monobutyl ether

CHID: 29755 CASRN: 29387-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I15

M4ID: 30008047 BRK

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	615.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	101.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.02	MAX_MED:	0.993	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fenofibrate

CHID: 29874 CASRN: 49562-28-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H05

M4ID: 30008081

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	590.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0792 MAX_MED: -0.997 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Glycoluril

CHID: 31380 CASRN: 496-46-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G02

M4ID: 30007751

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	616.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.551 MAX_MED: 0.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Perfluorononanoic acid

CHID: 31863 CASRN: 375-95-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C02

M4ID: 30008281

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	534.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.37	MAX_MED:	6.25	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Perfluorooctanoic acid
 CHID: 31865 CASRN: 335-67-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G02
 M4ID: 30007944

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	430.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.614 MAX_MED: -0.602 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Chlorhexidine diacetate

CHID: 32345 CASRN: 56-95-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J10

M4ID: 30007612

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	632.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.45 MAX_MED: 8.83 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dichlobenil

CHID: 32365 CASRN: 1194-65-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L21

M4ID: 30007897

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	428.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.9 MAX_MED: 1.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethenamid

CHID: 32376 CASRN: 87674-68-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G23

M4ID: 30007553

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	310.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.983 MAX_MED: 1.03 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethalfluralin

CHID: 32386 CASRN: 55283-68-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M22

M4ID: 30007696

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	516.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.44 MAX_MED: 2.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Formetanate hydrochloride

CHID: 32405 CASRN: 23422-53-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I16

M4ID: 30007594

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	495.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.48 MAX_MED: 3.06 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Profenofos

CHID: 32464 CASRN: 41198-08-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K05

M4ID: 30007631

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	426.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.58 MAX_MED: 2.47 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Triclopyr

CHID: 32497 CASRN: 55335-06-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E06

M4ID: 30008178

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	521.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.162 MAX_MED: 0.521 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Hydroxyethyl octyl sulfide

CHID: 32516 CASRN: 3547-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F16

M4ID: 30007954

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	479.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.3 MAX_MED: 3.04 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4,5-Dichloro-3H-1,2-dithiol-3-one

CHID: 32518 CASRN: 1192-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F24

M4ID: 30007753

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	449.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.85 MAX_MED: 3.98 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Acibenzolar-S-methyl

CHID: 32519 CASRN: 135158-54-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A11

M4ID: 30008269

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	284.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.43 MAX_MED: -3.43 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,2-Benzisothiazolin-3-one

CHID: 32523 CASRN: 2634-33-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E22

M4ID: 30008162

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	489.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.14 MAX_MED: 3.58 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Bifenazate

CHID: 32525 CASRN: 149877-41-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G22

M4ID: 30007552

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.15 MAX_MED: 4.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Etridiazole

CHID: 32547 CASRN: 2593-15-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E08

M4ID: 30007986

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	461.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.07 MAX_MED: 1.32 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fenpyroximate (Z,E)

CHID: 32550 CASRN: 111812-58-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E11

M4ID: 30007983

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	615.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.49 MAX_MED: 3.77 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fluazinam

CHID: 32551 CASRN: 79622-59-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A01

M4ID: 30007797

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	573.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.83 MAX_MED: 4.98 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Prallethrin
 CHID: 32572 CASRN: 23031-36-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078019
 M4ID: 30007827

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	525.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.9 MAX_MED: 6.64 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pyridaben
 CHID: 32573 CASRN: 96489-71-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M09
 M4ID: 30007683

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	623.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.63 MAX_MED: 4.26 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tefluthrin

CHID: 32577 CASRN: 79538-32-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078013

M4ID: 30007833

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	468.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.61 MAX_MED: 3.87 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cyproconazole

CHID: 32601 CASRN: 94361-06-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J03

M4ID: 30008035

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	521.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.19 MAX_MED: 7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fenitrothion

CHID: 32613 CASRN: 122-14-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091018

M4ID: 30008109

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	516.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0881 MAX_MED: 0.585 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Flumetsulam

CHID: 32615 CASRN: 98967-40-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078016

M4ID: 30007830

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	592.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.96 MAX_MED: -1.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pymetrozine

CHID: 32637 CASRN: 123312-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I20

M4ID: 30008042

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	516.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.55 MAX_MED: -1.82 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pyraclostrobin

CHID: 32638 CASRN: 175013-18-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L24

M4ID: 30007674

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	517.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.81 MAX_MED: 3.43 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pyridate

CHID: 32639 CASRN: 55512-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E13

M4ID: 30007981

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	534.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.02 MAX_MED: 2.26 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N-Ethylperfluorooctanesulfonamide

CHID: 32646 CASRN: 4151-50-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D04

M4ID: 30008204

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	621.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.8 MAX_MED: 0.361 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-(Thiocyanomethylthio)benzothiazole

CHID: 32647 CASRN: 21564-17-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K10

M4ID: 30007636

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	541.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.3 MAX_MED: 4.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Z-Tetrachlorvinphos

CHID: 32648 CASRN: 22248-79-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N21

M4ID: 30008130

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	437.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.61 MAX_MED: 2.83 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tetramethrin

CHID: 32649 CASRN: 7696-12-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091004

M4ID: 30008123

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	522.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.58 MAX_MED: 5.51 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Indoxacarb

CHID: 32690 CASRN: 173584-44-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H09

M4ID: 30008077

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	251.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.58 MAX_MED: 3.58 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Aldicarb sulfoxide

CHID: 33161 CASRN: 1646-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E16

M4ID: 30008168

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	606.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.99 MAX_MED: -2.99 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cyclopentanol

CHID: 33371 CASRN: 96-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A05

M4ID: 30008275

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	569.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0456 MAX_MED: 0.152 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tebufenpyrad

CHID: 34223 CASRN: 119168-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G06

M4ID: 30007940

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	617.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.77 MAX_MED: 6.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Icaridin

CHID: 34227 CASRN: 119515-38-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A07

M4ID: 30007791

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	559.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0503 MAX_MED: 1.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Chlorophenoxyacetic acid

CHID: 34282 CASRN: 122-88-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N08

M4ID: 30007706

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	473.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.3 MAX_MED: 1.71 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Denatonium saccharide

CHID: 34361 CASRN: 90823-38-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D19

M4ID: 30007999

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	461.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.845 MAX_MED: -0.0559 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Boscalid

CHID: 34392 CASRN: 188425-85-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B21

M4ID: 30008286

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	433.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.62 MAX_MED: 1.32 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Buprofezin

CHID: 34401 CASRN: 69327-76-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091003

M4ID: 30008124

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	565.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.48 MAX_MED: 2.62 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Butachlor
 CHID: 34402 CASRN: 23184-66-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P11
 M4ID: 30007771

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	587.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.6	MAX_MED: 2.87	BMAD: 3.31
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COFF: 9.93	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cinmethylin

CHID: 34456 CASRN: 87818-31-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F20

M4ID: 30008140

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	613.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 11 MAX_MED: 8.99 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Metconazole
 CHID: 34497 CASRN: 125116-23-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078011
 M4ID: 30007835

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	585.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.46 MAX_MED: 8.52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Desmedipham

CHID: 34518 CASRN: 13684-56-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M14

M4ID: 30007880

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	518.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.4 MAX_MED: 2.14 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diclosulam

CHID: 34528 CASRN: 145701-21-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K23

M4ID: 30007919

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	436.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.49 MAX_MED: 3.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Bromo-4-hydroxyacetophenone

CHID: 34576 CASRN: 2491-38-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D07

M4ID: 30007723

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.727 MAX_MED: -0.856 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fluazifop-butyl

CHID: 34612 CASRN: 69806-50-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I17

M4ID: 30007595

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	537.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.41 MAX_MED: -0.928 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Flufenpyr-ethyl

CHID: 34618 CASRN: 188489-07-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I07

M4ID: 30008055

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	536.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.911 MAX_MED: -0.178 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fluoxastrobin

CHID: 34625 CASRN: 361377-29-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J05

M4ID: 30008033

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	588.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.19 MAX_MED: 5.18 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Imazamox
CHID: 34664 CASRN: 114311-32-9
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J07
M4ID: 30007609

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.39 MAX_MED: 1.45 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isazofos

CHID: 34676 CASRN: 42509-80-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I18

M4ID: 30007596

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	492.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6 MAX_MED: 6.23 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isoxaflutole

CHID: 34723 CASRN: 141112-29-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091024

M4ID: 30007760

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	402.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.823 MAX_MED: 1.24 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Milbemectin (mixture of 70% Milbemcin A4, 30% I

CHID: 34742 CASRN: NOCAS_34742

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D01

M4ID: 30007729

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.63 MAX_MED: 3.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Monocrotophos

CHID: 34816 CASRN: 6923-22-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091009

M4ID: 30008118

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	585.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.115 MAX_MED: 0.403 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Propamocarb hydrochloride

CHID: 34849 CASRN: 25606-41-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F17

M4ID: 30007953

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	395.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.7 MAX_MED: 1.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fluazifop-P-butyl

CHID: 34855 CASRN: 79241-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F09

M4ID: 30007961

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	552.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.21 MAX_MED: 0.194 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Chloridazon
 CHID: 34872 CASRN: 1698-60-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E04
 M4ID: 30007990

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	526.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.483 MAX_MED: -0.396 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pyrimethanil

CHID: 34877 CASRN: 53112-28-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P04

M4ID: 30007764

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	543.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	9.29	MAX_MED:	8.92	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Spiromesifen

CHID: 34929 CASRN: 283594-90-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G01

M4ID: 30007752

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	609.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.43 MAX_MED: 2.94 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fosthiazate

CHID: 34930 CASRN: 98886-44-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091022

M4ID: 30007758

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	392.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.14 MAX_MED: 1.96 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Thiamethoxam

CHID: 34962 CASRN: 153719-23-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A17

M4ID: 30008314

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	579.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.82 MAX_MED: -4.25 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Thymo1

CHID: 34972 CASRN: 89-83-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E13

M4ID: 30008171

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	431.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.172 MAX_MED: 0.702 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tralkoxydim
 CHID: 34973 CASRN: 87820-88-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L10
 M4ID: 30007660

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	554.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.07 MAX_MED: 5.69 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium warfarin

CHID: 35010 CASRN: 129-06-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L17

M4ID: 30007901

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	432.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.65 MAX_MED: 1.48 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-(Hydroxymethyl)-5,5-dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 35152 CASRN: 116-25-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D17

M4ID: 30007713

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	332.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.06 MAX_MED: 1.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: alpha-Ionone

CHID: 35160 CASRN: 127-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D14

M4ID: 30008194

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	486.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.781 MAX_MED: -0.812 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Allethrin

CHID: 35180 CASRN: 584-79-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P05

M4ID: 30007765

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	543.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.55 MAX_MED: 6.36 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Codlure

CHID: 35288 CASRN: 33956-49-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I01

M4ID: 30008061

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	654.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.87 MAX_MED: 4.94 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,4-Dimethylnaphthalene

CHID: 35423 CASRN: 571-58-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K21

M4ID: 30007921

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	464.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.18 MAX_MED: 2.47 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Disiquonium chloride

CHID: 35589 CASRN: 68959-20-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J17

M4ID: 30007619

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	520.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.55 MAX_MED: 5.05 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-(8-Heptadecenyl)-2-imidazoline-1-ethanol

CHID: 36112 CASRN: 95-38-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K24

M4ID: 30007650

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	444.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.52 MAX_MED: 2.29 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium decyl sulfate

CHID: 36229 CASRN: 142-87-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H23

M4ID: 30007577

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	342.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.29 MAX_MED: 3.22 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Citralva

CHID: 36286 CASRN: 5146-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F12

M4ID: 30007958

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.62 MAX_MED: 1.51 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Disodium 4,4'-bis(2-sulfostyryl)biphenyl

CHID: 36467 CASRN: 27344-41-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C12

M4ID: 30007742

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	488.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.278 MAX_MED: 0.718 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Amiodarone hydrochloride

CHID: 37185 CASRN: 19774-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091017

M4ID: 30008110

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	521.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.72 MAX_MED: 2.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Perfluoroheptanoic acid

CHID: 37303 CASRN: 375-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N16

M4ID: 30008135

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	495.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.42 MAX_MED: 3.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Deisopropylatrazine

CHID: 37495 CASRN: 1007-28-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E03

M4ID: 30007991

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	426.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.937 MAX_MED: 1.09 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fenuron

CHID: 37551 CASRN: 101-42-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K08

M4ID: 30008006

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	565.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2 MAX_MED: -1.05 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Potassium perfluorohexanesulfonate

CHID: 37709 CASRN: 3871-99-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091002

M4ID: 30008125

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	371.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.17 MAX_MED: 1.67 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 5-Chlorosalicylanilide

CHID: 37749 CASRN: 4638-48-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I21

M4ID: 30007599

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	464.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.01	MAX_MED: 3.38	BMAD: 3.31
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COFF: 9.93	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Phenoxybenzoic acid

CHID: 38321 CASRN: 3739-38-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M15

M4ID: 30007689

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	421.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.73 MAX_MED: 3.82 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Chlorpyrifos oxon

CHID: 38666 CASRN: 5598-15-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B10

M4ID: 30008297

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	530.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0823 MAX_MED: -0.0907 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-4-nitroaniline

CHID: 38700 CASRN: 97-52-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G09

M4ID: 30008101

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	518.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.45 MAX_MED: 6.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,4-Cyclohexanedicarboxylic acid

CHID: 38788 CASRN: 1076-97-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H12

M4ID: 30007566

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	509.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.49 MAX_MED: 1.37 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Orange 7
 CHID: 38881 CASRN: 633-96-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091011
 M4ID: 30008116

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	547.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.75 MAX_MED: 1.27 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fluorescein

CHID: 38887 CASRN: 2321-07-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D24

M4ID: 30008184

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	478.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.12 MAX_MED: 2.38 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Basic Blue 7

CHID: 38888 CASRN: 2390-60-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K11

M4ID: 30007637

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	581.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.06 MAX_MED: 5.33 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethyl propionate

CHID: 40110 CASRN: 105-37-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B03

M4ID: 30008253

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	562	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.5 MAX_MED: -0.594 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethyl butyrate

CHID: 40111 CASRN: 105-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H02

M4ID: 30008084

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	577.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.31 MAX_MED: 3.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethyl heptanoate

CHID: 40112 CASRN: 106-30-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I16

M4ID: 30008046

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	568.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.02 MAX_MED: -2.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Trifloxysulfuron-sodium

CHID: 40222 CASRN: 199119-58-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P23

M4ID: 30007783

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	440.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.141 MAX_MED: 0.163 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Butylene carbonate
 CHID: 40342 CASRN: 4437-85-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L19
 M4ID: 30007669

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	478.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.477 MAX_MED: -0.648 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dinocap
 CHID: 40352 CASRN: 39300-45-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E22
 M4ID: 30007972

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	485.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.53	MAX_MED: 1.88	BMAD: 3.31
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COFF: 9.93	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isoxadifen-ethyl

CHID: 40360 CASRN: 163520-33-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H13

M4ID: 30007567

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	465.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.87 MAX_MED: 1.96 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Niclosamide

CHID: 40362 CASRN: 50-65-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A24

M4ID: 30008307

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	576.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.96 MAX_MED: 5.58 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Forskolin

CHID: 40484 CASRN: 66575-29-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J23

M4ID: 30007625

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	341.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.88 MAX_MED: 1.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Butyl benzoate

CHID: 40694 CASRN: 136-60-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B15

M4ID: 30008292

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	444.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.74	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.16 MAX_MED: 1.09 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Trimethoxyphenylsilane

CHID: 40700 CASRN: 2996-92-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D16

M4ID: 30007714

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	407.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.15 MAX_MED: 1.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Octyl gallate

CHID: 40713 CASRN: 1034-01-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K19

M4ID: 30007645

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	537.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.33 MAX_MED: 7.98 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Morin hydrate

CHID: 40776 CASRN: 654055-01-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C19

M4ID: 30007735

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	593.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.83 MAX_MED: -1.26 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-tert-Butyl-4-methoxyphenol

CHID: 40788 CASRN: 121-00-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B02

M4ID: 30008305

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	482.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.4 MAX_MED: 2.53 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pyridoxine hydrochloride

CHID: 40792 CASRN: 58-56-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078009

M4ID: 30007837

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	526.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.75 MAX_MED: 3.91 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium iodide

CHID: 41125 CASRN: 7681-82-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L12

M4ID: 30007662

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	535.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.967 MAX_MED: 1.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: (2-Nitro-1-propenyl)benzene

CHID: 41188 CASRN: 705-60-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F04

M4ID: 30008156

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	536.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.19 MAX_MED: 8.51 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,3,5-Triisopropylbenzene

CHID: 41232 CASRN: 717-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G12

M4ID: 30007934

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	493.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.25 MAX_MED: 1.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,4-Diaminoanthraquinone

CHID: 41252 CASRN: 128-95-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N07

M4ID: 30007705

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	444.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.11 MAX_MED: 2.09 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Hexyl-1-decanol
 CHID: 41265 CASRN: 2425-77-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091012
 M4ID: 30008115

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	599.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.479 MAX_MED: 1.15 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Phenyl-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione

CHID: 41274 CASRN: 941-69-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C01

M4ID: 30008231

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	626.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.62 MAX_MED: 5.47 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Monolaurin

CHID: 41275 CASRN: 142-18-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L23

M4ID: 30007673

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	445.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.123 MAX_MED: 0.148 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2'-Acetonaphthone

CHID: 41389 CASRN: 93-08-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G22

M4ID: 30008088

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	518.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.764 MAX_MED: 1.31 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: R-(-)-Carvone

CHID: 41413 CASRN: 6485-40-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E12

M4ID: 30007982

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	448.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0171 MAX_MED: 0.31 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 7-(Dimethylamino)-4-methylcoumarin

CHID: 41422 CASRN: 87-01-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D20

M4ID: 30008188

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	586.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.92 MAX_MED: -1.78 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Methylbutyl isovalerate

CHID: 41440 CASRN: 2445-77-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F11

M4ID: 30008149

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	465.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.249 MAX_MED: 0.425 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: (3Z)-3-Hexenyl acetate

CHID: 41484 CASRN: 3681-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E23

M4ID: 30008161

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	416.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.8 MAX_MED: 2.24 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Phenylhexane

CHID: 41492 CASRN: 4468-42-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I09

M4ID: 30008053

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.27 MAX_MED: 2.24 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: (4Z)-4-Decenal

CHID: 41514 CASRN: 21662-09-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K09

M4ID: 30008005

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	527.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.07 MAX_MED: 4.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Morpholinepropanamine

CHID: 41521 CASRN: 123-00-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B10

M4ID: 30008246

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	586.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.526 MAX_MED: -0.137 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 7-Ethyl-2-methyl-4-undecanol sulfate, sodium salt

CHID: 41530 CASRN: 139-88-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N19

M4ID: 30008132

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	518.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.19 MAX_MED: -0.666 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dihydromyrcenol

CHID: 41557 CASRN: 53219-21-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L16

M4ID: 30007902

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	561.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.13 MAX_MED: -1.69 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Arabinose

CHID: 41610 CASRN: 147-81-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C07

M4ID: 30007747

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	397.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.854 MAX_MED: 1.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium m-xylene-4-sulfonate

CHID: 41639 CASRN: 827-21-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G20

M4ID: 30008090

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	519.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.24 MAX_MED: -2.31 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Yellow 34, monosodium salt

CHID: 41646 CASRN: 6359-90-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E14

M4ID: 30008170

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	486.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.935 MAX_MED: -1.07 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Hydroxybenzonitrile

CHID: 41661 CASRN: 611-20-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G07

M4ID: 30007939

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	418.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.12 MAX_MED: 0.395 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Bromophenol blue

CHID: 41682 CASRN: 115-39-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C02

M4ID: 30008230

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	728.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.47 MAX_MED: 6.31 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Butylphthalenesulfonic acid sodium salt

CHID: 41703 CASRN: 25638-17-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F05

M4ID: 30008155

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	447.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.333 MAX_MED: -0.606 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Violet 12, disodium salt

CHID: 41715 CASRN: 6625-46-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K14

M4ID: 30008000

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	477	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.74 MAX_MED: 4.36 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Yellow 3 disodium salt

CHID: 41721 CASRN: 8004-92-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F14

M4ID: 30007956

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	428.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.94 MAX_MED: 3.24 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Citronellal

CHID: 41790 CASRN: 106-23-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C03

M4ID: 30008229

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	462.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.35 MAX_MED: -0.779 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dibutyl decanedioate

CHID: 41847 CASRN: 109-43-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E03

M4ID: 30008181

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	511.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.345 MAX_MED: -0.216 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diethyl phosphite

CHID: 41861 CASRN: 762-04-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N15

M4ID: 30007855

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	537.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.09 MAX_MED: -1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethyl diethanolamine
 CHID: 41955 CASRN: 139-87-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E19
 M4ID: 30007975

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	461.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.467 MAX_MED: 0.298 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethyl orthoformate

CHID: 41957 CASRN: 122-51-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P05

M4ID: 30007817

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	548.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.239 MAX_MED: -0.162 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Flufenoxuron

CHID: 41978 CASRN: 101463-69-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E01

M4ID: 30008183

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	673.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.59 MAX_MED: 3.59 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fluoroacetic acid

CHID: 41981 CASRN: 144-49-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B20

M4ID: 30008287

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	481.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.303 MAX_MED: -0.528 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Glyceryl monoricinoleate

CHID: 42007 CASRN: 1323-38-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M07

M4ID: 30007887

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	572.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.5 MAX_MED: -2.85 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isoborneol

CHID: 42060 CASRN: 124-76-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091021

M4ID: 30007757

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	405.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.497 MAX_MED: -0.483 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Dodecylmorpholine

CHID: 42171 CASRN: 1541-81-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A23

M4ID: 30008308

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	610.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.495 MAX_MED: -0.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N,N'-Dibutylthiourea

CHID: 42187 CASRN: 109-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D12

M4ID: 30007718

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	449.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.38 MAX_MED: 1.48 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N,N-Diisopropylaniline

CHID: 42189 CASRN: 4107-98-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N08

M4ID: 30007862

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	539.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.673 MAX_MED: -0.756 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N,N'-Dimethylthiourea

CHID: 42191 CASRN: 534-13-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091016

M4ID: 30008111

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	477.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.13 MAX_MED: 1.53 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Butyl lactate

CHID: 42196 CASRN: 138-22-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A01

M4ID: 30008279

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	801.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.25 MAX_MED: -2.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Dodecyl-2-pyrrolidinone

CHID: 42206 CASRN: 2687-96-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M11

M4ID: 30007883

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	560.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.44 MAX_MED: 7.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N-Methyldioctylamine

CHID: 42209 CASRN: 4455-26-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091010

M4ID: 30008117

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	648.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	10.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.38 MAX_MED: 0.916 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Propylbenzene

CHID: 42219 CASRN: 103-65-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B11

M4ID: 30008245

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	521.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.96 MAX_MED: -1.62 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Oleyl sarcosine

CHID: 42243 CASRN: 110-25-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I11

M4ID: 30007589

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	576.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.35 MAX_MED: 2.29 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethoxydimethylsilane

CHID: 42379 CASRN: 1112-39-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I12

M4ID: 30007590

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	502.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.69 MAX_MED: 2.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium (2-pyridylthio)-N-oxide

CHID: 42390 CASRN: 3811-73-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E11

M4ID: 30008173

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	522.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.49 MAX_MED: 3.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium 4-methylbenzenesulfonate

CHID: 42415 CASRN: 657-84-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C10

M4ID: 30008222

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	536.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.63	MAX_MED:	0.796	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sulfosuccinic acid

CHID: 42426 CASRN: 5138-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P19

M4ID: 30007779

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	561.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.899 MAX_MED: -1.23 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tetradecanoic acid, 2,3-dihydroxypropyl ester

CHID: 42454 CASRN: 589-68-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E14

M4ID: 30007980

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	540.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.31 MAX_MED: 2.29 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Clove leaf oil

CHID: 44175 CASRN: 8000-34-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C09

M4ID: 30008223

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	465.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.01 MAX_MED: 2.06 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N,N-Dibutyl-N-methylbutan-1-aminium chloride

CHID: 44443 CASRN: 56375-79-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P09

M4ID: 30007813

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	498.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.39 MAX_MED: 1.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-(6-tert-Butyl-1,1-dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-im

CHID: 44536 CASRN: 13171-00-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M21

M4ID: 30007695

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	433.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.48	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.826 MAX_MED: -0.359 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: C.I. Disperse Orange 37

CHID: 44538 CASRN: 13301-61-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D23

M4ID: 30007995

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	462.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.46 MAX_MED: 2.55 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,6,10-Trimethyl-2,6,10-triazaundecane

CHID: 44564 CASRN: 3855-32-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L15

M4ID: 30007665

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	437.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.36 MAX_MED: 2.11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 6:2 Fluorotelomer alcohol

CHID: 44572 CASRN: 647-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D02

M4ID: 30007728

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.31 MAX_MED: -1.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: MON-4660

CHID: 44575 CASRN: 71526-07-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L13

M4ID: 30007905

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	455.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.74 MAX_MED: 7.49 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-tert-Butyl-4-ethylphenol

CHID: 44581 CASRN: 96-70-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N04

M4ID: 30007702

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	551.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.56 MAX_MED: 7.94 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Glycidyl trimethylammonium chloride

CHID: 44643 CASRN: 3033-77-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F21

M4ID: 30007949

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	403.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.71 MAX_MED: 1.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Acid Red 337

CHID: 44713 CASRN: 67786-14-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L07

M4ID: 30007657

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	509.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.51 MAX_MED: 4.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Terpinyl propionate

CHID: 44833 CASRN: 80-27-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P15

M4ID: 30007807

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	605.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.5 MAX_MED: -3.14 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Triallyl trimellitate

CHID: 44901 CASRN: 2694-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H11

M4ID: 30007565

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	646.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.838 MAX_MED: 0.75 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isopropyl triethanolamine titanate

CHID: 44928 CASRN: 36673-16-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C10

M4ID: 30007744

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	489.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.36 MAX_MED: 1.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Octadecyl sulfate sodium salt

CHID: 47103 CASRN: 1120-04-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091013

M4ID: 30008114

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	504.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.7 MAX_MED: 4.73 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: tert-Butylbenzene

CHID: 47138 CASRN: 98-06-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F02

M4ID: 30008158

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	653.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.11 MAX_MED: -1.17 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Darbufelone mesylate

CHID: 47246 CASRN: 139340-56-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E01

M4ID: 30007993

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	447.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.064 MAX_MED: -0.0925 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: CI-1018

CHID: 47248 CASRN: NOCAS_47248

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F13

M4ID: 30007957

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.37 MAX_MED: 2.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: CP-457920

CHID: 47254 CASRN: 220860-50-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N14

M4ID: 30007856

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.13 MAX_MED: 4.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Zamifenacin
 CHID: 47257 CASRN: 127308-82-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B24
 M4ID: 30008232

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	550.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.1 MAX_MED: 5.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: PharmaGSID_47263

CHID: 47263 CASRN: 349495-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078024

M4ID: 30007822

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	596.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.62 MAX_MED: -1.78 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Besonprodil

CHID: 47270 CASRN: 253450-09-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E02

M4ID: 30008182

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	711.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.52 MAX_MED: -1.26 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: CP-409092

CHID: 47276 CASRN: 194098-25-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J01

M4ID: 30008037

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	534.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.17 MAX_MED: 1.17 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: CP-457677

CHID: 47278 CASRN: 214535-77-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N01

M4ID: 30007869

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	617.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.433 MAX_MED: 0.501 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: CP-607366

CHID: 47280 CASRN: 289716-94-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L01

M4ID: 30007917

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	688.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.34 MAX_MED: 8.29 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: CP-671305

CHID: 47282 CASRN: 445295-04-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K07

M4ID: 30008007

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	597.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.94 MAX_MED: -3.05 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: PHA-00543613

CHID: 47284 CASRN: 478149-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H01

M4ID: 30007555

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	413.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.582 MAX_MED: 1.14 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: UK-416244

CHID: 47290 CASRN: 402910-27-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M13

M4ID: 30007687

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	466.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5 MAX_MED: 5.19 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: CP-863187

CHID: 47294 CASRN: 668981-02-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J14

M4ID: 30008024

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	463.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.956 MAX_MED: 0.403 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: CP-422935

CHID: 47299 CASRN: NOCAS_47299

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J01

M4ID: 30007603

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	382.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0966 MAX_MED: -0.113 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: CP-608039

CHID: 47305 CASRN: NOCAS_47305

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M02

M4ID: 30007892

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	601.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.21 MAX_MED: 1.86 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: UK-156819

CHID: 47309 CASRN: 162706-14-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N09

M4ID: 30007707

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	545.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.2 MAX_MED: 1.05 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: GW473178E methyl benzene sulphonic acid

CHID: 47313 CASRN: 263553-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C13

M4ID: 30007741

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	447.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.431 MAX_MED: 0.732 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: MK-812

CHID: 47335 CASRN: 851916-42-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A18

M4ID: 30008313

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	606.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -4.06 MAX_MED: -4.05 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: SR125047

CHID: 47342 CASRN: NOCAS_47342

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F01

M4ID: 30008159

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	662.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.56 MAX_MED: 9.68 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: SSR162369

CHID: 47346 CASRN: NOCAS_47346

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C05

M4ID: 30008227

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	413.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.184 MAX_MED: 0.11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: SSR180711

CHID: 47359 CASRN: 298198-52-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P24

M4ID: 30007798

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	571.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.08 MAX_MED: -1.67 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: SSR150106
 CHID: 47362 CASRN: NOCAS_47362
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E15
 M4ID: 30008169

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	543.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.2 MAX_MED: 5.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Volinanserin

CHID: 47363 CASRN: 139290-65-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P13

M4ID: 30007773

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	470.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.81 MAX_MED: 3.84 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: SSR 103800

CHID: 47364 CASRN: 1075752-90-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P01

M4ID: 30007821

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	697.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.71	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.34 MAX_MED: 7.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: AVE3295

CHID: 47372 CASRN: 478263-98-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K02

M4ID: 30008012

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	593.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.93 MAX_MED: 3.04 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: SAR377142

CHID: 47385 CASRN: NOCAS_47385

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N17

M4ID: 30008134

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	484.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.107 MAX_MED: -0.339 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Grinstad Soft-N-Safe

CHID: 47394 CASRN: NOCAS_47394

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078008

M4ID: 30007838

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	597.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.93 MAX_MED: -0.793 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diisononyl cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate

CHID: 47395 CASRN: 166412-78-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B03

M4ID: 30008304

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	510.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.769 MAX_MED: -0.753 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Potassium chlorate

CHID: 47448 CASRN: 3811-04-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H16

M4ID: 30007570

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	476.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.41 MAX_MED: 2.71 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Acid Yellow 11

CHID: 47451 CASRN: 6359-82-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A13

M4ID: 30007785

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	608.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.62 MAX_MED: -2.47 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Hexanedioic acid, di-C7-9-branched and linear ;

CHID: 47517 CASRN: 68515-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K09

M4ID: 30007635

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	535.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.153 MAX_MED: -0.00899 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: C10-21 alkanesulfonic acids phenyl esters

CHID: 47526 CASRN: 91082-17-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B09

M4ID: 30008247

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	559.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.7 MAX_MED: 1.44 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Adipic acid, polypropyleneglycol, laurate

CHID: 47527 CASRN: 66456-53-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L08

M4ID: 30007910

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	479.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.3 MAX_MED: -2.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Trioctyl trimellitate
 CHID: 47533 CASRN: 89-04-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L03
 M4ID: 30007653

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	474.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0811 MAX_MED: 0.212 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,4-Heptanolide

CHID: 47611 CASRN: 105-21-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J13

M4ID: 30007615

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	429.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.48	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.04 MAX_MED: 2.75 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cremophor EL

CHID: 47696 CASRN: 61791-12-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L02

M4ID: 30007916

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	702.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.3 MAX_MED: 1.72 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Igepal CO-890

CHID: 47708 CASRN: NOCAS_47708

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J08

M4ID: 30008030

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	604.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.32 MAX_MED: -2.58 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: FR167356

CHID: 48174 CASRN: 174185-16-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G05

M4ID: 30007941

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	527.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.74 MAX_MED: 5.72 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Melengestrol acetate

CHID: 48184 CASRN: 2919-66-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C15

M4ID: 30008217

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	556.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.87 MAX_MED: 3.66 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Lauryl gallate

CHID: 48189 CASRN: 1166-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H01

M4ID: 30008085

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	654.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.97 MAX_MED: 6.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methyl abietate

CHID: 48190 CASRN: 127-25-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I14

M4ID: 30007592

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	464.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.74 MAX_MED: 3.39 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Propylcyclohexanone

CHID: 48198 CASRN: 40649-36-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C14

M4ID: 30008218

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	536.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.99 MAX_MED: -1.18 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cyclobutyl phenyl ketone

CHID: 48201 CASRN: 5407-98-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078014

M4ID: 30007832

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	450.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.86 MAX_MED: 4.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isopropyl phenyl ketone

CHID: 48202 CASRN: 611-70-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G15

M4ID: 30008095

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	440.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.73 MAX_MED: 2.47 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Chloropentylbenzene

CHID: 48206 CASRN: 79098-20-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C14

M4ID: 30007740

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	472.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.873 MAX_MED: 1.43 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methyl 2-methylbenzoate

CHID: 48208 CASRN: 89-71-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N04

M4ID: 30007866

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	477.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.15 MAX_MED: 1.15 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48505

CHID: 48505 CASRN: NOCAS_48505

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078007

M4ID: 30007839

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	524.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.547 MAX_MED: 1.23 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: HMR1171 trifluoroacetate (1:1)

CHID: 48522 CASRN: NOCAS_48522

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M08

M4ID: 30007886

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	575.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.853 MAX_MED: -0.41 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Aminoanthraquinone
 CHID: 20068 CASRN: 117-79-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D15
 M4ID: 30008193 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	981.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	52.74	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.65 MAX_MED: -3.39 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pentaerythritol dibromide

CHID: 20164 CASRN: 3296-90-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I12

M4ID: 30008050 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	855.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	26.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-3.89	MAX_MED:	-2.27	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Blue 74

CHID: 20190 CASRN: 860-22-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091019

M4ID: 30008108

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	787.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	18.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.42 MAX_MED: -3.09 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benzyl butyl phthalate

CHID: 20205 CASRN: 85-68-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P16

M4ID: 30007776 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.16e-09	1.62	0.342
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.4e-10	2.05	1.23	2.3	5.16
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	939.68	945.68	949.68
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	42.97	42.97	42.97

MAX_MEAN: 0.0702 MAX_MED: 0.0539 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Butylparaben

CHID: 20209 CASRN: 94-26-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B17

M4ID: 30008290 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1097.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	101.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.78	MAX_MED:	-1.07	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-tert-Butylphenol

CHID: 20221 CASRN: 98-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B22

M4ID: 30008234

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	733.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	13.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.836	MAX_MED:	-1.23	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Carbofuran

CHID: 20249 CASRN: 1563-66-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P06

M4ID: 30007816 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	883.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	31.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-5	MAX_MED:	-3.59	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Catechol

CHID: 20257 CASRN: 120-80-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M18

M4ID: 30007692

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.26	1.84	8
sd:	1.23	0.116	9.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.23e-07	0.164	6.3	0.556	8.74
sd:	0.000406	1060	40300	651	114000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	596.37	601.07	606.37
PROB:	0.91	0.09	0.01
RMSE:	6.76	6.73	6.76

MAX_MEAN: 3.25 MAX_MED: 4.03 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.09

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Chloro-1,2-diaminobenzene

CHID: 20283 CASRN: 95-83-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M06

M4ID: 30007680

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.65e-10	2.75	2.24
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.37	-2.79	2.64	0.0553	9.06
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	590.99	596.99	591.58
PROB:	0.56	0.03	0.41
RMSE:	6.6	6.6	6.42

MAX_MEAN: 3.47 MAX_MED: 2.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.44

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dehydroepiandrosterone

CHID: 20379 CASRN: 53-43-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D18

M4ID: 30007712 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.03	2.05	8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.29e-06	-0.609	6.42	-0.343	6.33
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	869.96	875.89	879.96
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	29.24	29.24	29.24

MAX_MEAN: 2.14 MAX_MED: 5.24 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,4-D Butyl ester
 CHID: 20443 CASRN: 94-80-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H13
 M4ID: 30008073

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.06e-07 2.78 4.57
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.31 -1.22 3.93 -0.573 11.2
 sd: 94.4 35.4 396 312 6100

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	658.37	664.37	667.59
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	8.85	8.85	8.83

MAX_MEAN: 2.04 MAX_MED: 1.91 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diethylene glycol
 CHID: 20462 CASRN: 111-46-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F18
 M4ID: 30008142

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	583.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.14 MAX_MED: -0.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,6-Dinitrotoluene
CHID: 20528 CASRN: 606-20-2
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J06
M4ID: 30008032 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	866.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	35.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 15 MAX_MED: -1.89 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Glycerol

CHID: 20663 CASRN: 56-81-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C17

M4ID: 30008215

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	670.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.612 MAX_MED: -1.74 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Chloro-1,2-propanediol

CHID: 20664 CASRN: 96-24-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I09

M4ID: 30007587 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	888.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-3.76	MAX_MED:	-4.19	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Propham

CHID: 20766 CASRN: 122-42-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A10

M4ID: 30008270

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	662.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.84 MAX_MED: -5.03 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,2'-Methylenebis(4-methyl-6-tert-butylphenol)

CHID: 20870 CASRN: 119-47-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P16

M4ID: 30007806

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	617.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.99 MAX_MED: 3.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Nitriлотriacetic acid
CHID: 20939 CASRN: 139-13-9
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A22
M4ID: 30008258

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	769	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	16.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-5.37	MAX_MED:	-4.3	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Nitrofurantoin
 CHID: 20972 CASRN: 67-20-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H02
 M4ID: 30007556

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.46e-09	1.87	1.23
sd:	0.00013	6280	47900

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.384	1.27	5.32	1.6	9.27
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.08	145.08	149.08
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3	3	3

MAX_MEAN: -0.454 MAX_MED: 0.437 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N-Nitrosodibutylamine
 CHID: 21026 CASRN: 924-16-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J15
 M4ID: 30007617

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.52e-09 1.97 1.25
 sd: 2.99e-05 1630 35200

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 3.77e-09 1.84 1.52 2.15 5.51
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	668.78	674.78	678.78
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	10.14	10.14	10.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.916 MAX_MED: 0.946 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,3-Benzenediamine

CHID: 21137 CASRN: 108-45-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A21

M4ID: 30008259

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	599.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.729	MAX_MED:	-0.104	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Picloram
 CHID: 21160 CASRN: 1918-02-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K18
 M4ID: 30007644 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.98e-09 1.33 1.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 9.42e-09 0.966 1.97 1.47 5.7
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	824.02	830.02	834.02
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	22.24	22.24	22.24

MAX_MEAN: -1 MAX_MED: 1.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Propyl gallate
 CHID: 21201 CASRN: 121-79-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B12
 M4ID: 30008244

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.36e-07 2.62 5.27
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.69e-10 2.26 3.99 2.65 6.97
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	701.71	707.71	711.71
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	11.63	11.63	11.63

MAX_MEAN: 5.15 MAX_MED: 6.86 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Thiabendazole
 CHID: 21337 CASRN: 148-79-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A05
 M4ID: 30007793

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	695.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	10.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.64 MAX_MED: -2.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,2,4-Trimethylbenzene

CHID: 21402 CASRN: 95-63-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I08

M4ID: 30007586 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.1e-08	2.8	1.45
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.41	-0.971	7.7	0.0949	11.6
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	801.24	807.24	809.88
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	33.29	33.29	33.28

MAX_MEAN: 2.24 MAX_MED: 1.99 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Octanal

CHID: 21643 CASRN: 124-13-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E18

M4ID: 30008166

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	681.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	10.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.969 MAX_MED: -0.796 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Octanoic acid
 CHID: 21645 CASRN: 124-07-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P07
 M4ID: 30007815

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	710.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.61 MAX_MED: -4.01 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethyl sulfoxide
 CHID: 21735 CASRN: 67-68-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B11
 M4ID: 30008296 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.4e-07 2.74 4.08
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 3.7e-11 2.29 2 2.9 5
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	686.72	692.72	696.72
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	12.45	12.45	12.45

MAX_MEAN: 1.46 MAX_MED: 2.15 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diethyl phthalate

CHID: 21780 CASRN: 84-66-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J16

M4ID: 30007618

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.25e-09	2.38	1.76
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.39	-2.68	3.64	0.774	17.9
sd:	1.21	3.23	617	2.47	221

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	632.53	638.53	641.12
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.91	7.91	7.87

MAX_MEAN: 2.07 MAX_MED: 1.83 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Methyl-2,4-pentanedio1

CHID: 21885 CASRN: 107-41-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H07

M4ID: 30008079

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	669.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	10.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.58 MAX_MED: -0.926 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Phenyl salicylate

CHID: 21957 CASRN: 118-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L19

M4ID: 30007899

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	719.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	12.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.43 MAX_MED: -1.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Phenoxyethanol
 CHID: 21976 CASRN: 122-99-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C22
 M4ID: 30008210

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.44e-09	2.13	0.976
sd:	9.08e-06	5200	19000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.01e-11	1.52	2.02	1.93	5.18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	648.65	654.65	658.65
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	8.87	8.87	8.87

MAX_MEAN: 0.252 MAX_MED: 0.569 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: γ -Decanolactone
 CHID: 22109 CASRN: 706-14-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D17
 M4ID: 30008191

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	566.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0608 MAX_MED: 0.741 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Hexyloxyaniline

CHID: 22288 CASRN: 39905-57-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P02

M4ID: 30007820

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.13e-09	2.21	1.41
sd:	5.1e-06	2970	19500

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.45	-1.21	4.38	-0.0348	13.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	917.9	923.9	927.6
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	10.69	10.69	10.68

MAX_MEAN: 1.19 MAX_MED: 2.17 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Vinclozolin

CHID: 22361 CASRN: 50471-44-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F22

M4ID: 30007948

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	645.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.329 MAX_MED: -0.569 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 5alpha-Dihydrotestosterone

CHID: 22364 CASRN: 521-18-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C11

M4ID: 30007743

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	809.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	20.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-3.73	MAX_MED:	-3.12	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 17alpha-Estradiol
 CHID: 22377 CASRN: 57-91-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K06
 M4ID: 30008008 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	854.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	26.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.96 MAX_MED: 4.31 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone
 CHID: 22406 CASRN: 131-56-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D24
 M4ID: 30007994

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.06e-07 2.74 4.4
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.3e-09 0.0167 7.44 0.345 5.12
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	645.5	651.5	655.5
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.58	9.58	9.58

MAX_MEAN: -0.0562 MAX_MED: 4.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Diaminobiphenyl methane

CHID: 22422 CASRN: 101-77-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P18

M4ID: 30007804

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	670.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	10.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-3.26	MAX_MED:	-3.5	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diphenolic acid
 CHID: 22436 CASRN: 126-00-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L13
 M4ID: 30007663 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.67e-09 1.48 1.82
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.04e-07 0.305 2.87 0.643 6.22
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	762.93	768.93	772.93
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	16.48	16.48	16.48

MAX_MEAN: 0.49 MAX_MED: 1.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Polydimethylsiloxane

CHID: 23833 CASRN: 9016-00-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A12

M4ID: 30007786

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	690.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.53 MAX_MED: -1.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Molinate
 CHID: 24206 CASRN: 2212-67-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I13
 M4ID: 30008049

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 9.96e-10 1.66 1.74
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.29e-10 1.3 2.34 1.75 5.75
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	594.17	600.17	604.17
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.38	6.38	6.38

MAX_MEAN: 1.21 MAX_MED: 1.23 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pendimethalin
 CHID: 24245 CASRN: 40487-42-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P20
 M4ID: 30007780

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	642.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.18 MAX_MED: -1.87 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Terbacil

CHID: 24317 CASRN: 5902-51-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K05

M4ID: 30008009

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	657.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	9.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.26 MAX_MED: -1.76 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benzothiazole

CHID: 24586 CASRN: 95-16-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A02

M4ID: 30008278

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	874.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -5.47 MAX_MED: -5.34 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benzyl salicylate

CHID: 24598 CASRN: 118-58-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F07

M4ID: 30008153

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	818.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	22.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.74 MAX_MED: -0.903 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Butanal oxime

CHID: 24664 CASRN: 110-69-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A12

M4ID: 30008268

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	687.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	10.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -7.73 MAX_MED: -7.57 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Butyl glycidyl ether

CHID: 24691 CASRN: 2426-08-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B09

M4ID: 30008298 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.22e-08	1.08	1.59
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.13e-09	1.12	1.64	1.41	5.75
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	889.21	895.21	899.21
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	31.55	31.55	31.55

MAX_MEAN: 0.366 MAX_MED: 0.278 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Troclosesene

CHID: 24993 CASRN: 2782-57-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A19

M4ID: 30008312

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	671.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	10.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-2.63	MAX_MED:	-3.26	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dicyclopentadiene

CHID: 25023 CASRN: 77-73-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E04

M4ID: 30008180

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	724.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	13.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.45	MAX_MED:	-0.315	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethyl succinate
 CHID: 25152 CASRN: 106-65-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A24
 M4ID: 30008256

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	628.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.52	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.13 MAX_MED: -2.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 6-Hydroxy-2-naphthyl disulfide

CHID: 25429 CASRN: 6088-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D13

M4ID: 30007717

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	800.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	20.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.138 MAX_MED: -0.0417 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Maltol

CHID: 25523 CASRN: 118-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B21

M4ID: 30008235

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	555.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.26 MAX_MED: 1.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Triphenyl phosphite

CHID: 26252 CASRN: 101-02-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H17

M4ID: 30007571

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	594.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.479 MAX_MED: -0.23 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Acetyl tributyl citrate
 CHID: 26446 CASRN: 77-90-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H16
 M4ID: 30008070

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.47 1.88 8
 sd: 1.47 0.125 7.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.77e-09 0.0522 2.46 0.486 6.4
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	622.12	624.93	632.12
PROB:	0.8	0.2	0.01
RMSE:	7.14	7.05	7.14

MAX_MEAN: 3.04 MAX_MED: 2.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.2

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: (2Z)-3,7-Dimethylocta-2,6-dien-1-ol

CHID: 26728 CASRN: 106-25-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B18

M4ID: 30008238

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	865.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	27.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-8.4	MAX_MED:	-8.45	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N-Methylphthalimide
 CHID: 27198 CASRN: 550-44-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P08
 M4ID: 30007814

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	624.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.59 MAX_MED: -3.68 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-(Methylthio)propanal

CHID: 27528 CASRN: 3268-49-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A20

M4ID: 30008311

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	640.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -4.45 MAX_MED: -4.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N-Butylbenzenesulfonamide

CHID: 27540 CASRN: 3622-84-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H09

M4ID: 30007563 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.89e-08	2.27	1.01
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.69	1.36	7.98	1.66	17.2
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	698.55	704.55	708.35
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	24.41	24.41	24.44

MAX_MEAN: 0.766 MAX_MED: 1.35 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Malic acid

CHID: 27640 CASRN: 6915-15-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P12

M4ID: 30007810

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	663.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-4.32	MAX_MED:	-4.4	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Glyceryl monooleate

CHID: 27875 CASRN: 25496-72-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P22

M4ID: 30007782

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	601.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.33 MAX_MED: -2.23 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3,7-Dimethyl-3-octanol
 CHID: 29110 CASRN: 78-69-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F13
 M4ID: 30008147

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.12e-09 1.68 1.47
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.44e-10 1.52 2.04 2.26 5.03
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	596.1	602.1	606.1
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.61	6.61	6.61

MAX_MEAN: 0.778 MAX_MED: 0.689 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,1-Bis(3,4-dimethylphenyl)ethane

CHID: 29223 CASRN: 1742-14-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B16

M4ID: 30008240

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	603.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.14	MAX_MED:	1.46	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Acetyl cedrene

CHID: 29353 CASRN: 32388-55-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B17

M4ID: 30008239

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	734.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	14.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.86 MAX_MED: 4.46 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 8:2 Fluorotelomer alcohol

CHID: 29904 CASRN: 678-39-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E02

M4ID: 30007992

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	579.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.72 MAX_MED: -1.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dipentyl phthalate

CHID: 31131 CASRN: 131-18-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N20

M4ID: 30008131

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	620.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2 MAX_MED: -2.12 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Clodinafop-propargyl

CHID: 32354 CASRN: 105512-06-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B04

M4ID: 30008303

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	661.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.54 MAX_MED: -1.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Clomazone

CHID: 32355 CASRN: 81777-89-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P09

M4ID: 30007769

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	700.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.925 MAX_MED: -0.717 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fenhexamid

CHID: 32549 CASRN: 126833-17-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E20

M4ID: 30008164

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.86e-09	0.968	1.23
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.59e-08	0.134	7.96	0.431	5.96
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	735.61	741.61	745.61
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	14.56	14.56	14.56

MAX_MEAN: 1.51 MAX_MED: 0.398 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Flufenacet

CHID: 32552 CASRN: 142459-58-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N16

M4ID: 30007854

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	560.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.32 MAX_MED: 1.21 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Amino-1,2,4-triazole
 CHID: 33058 CASRN: 584-13-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P24
 M4ID: 30007711

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.42e-10 1.33 1.17
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.28e-10 1.55 2.21 1.82 4.81
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	572.91	578.91	582.91
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.78	5.78	5.78

MAX_MEAN: 0.455 MAX_MED: 0.0124 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 17-Methyltestosterone
CHID: 33664 CASRN: 58-18-4
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A14
M4ID: 30007784 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	879.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	30.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-5.8	MAX_MED:	-5.87	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Haloperidol
 CHID: 34150 CASRN: 52-86-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A14
 M4ID: 30008266

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.85e-09 0.976 0.93
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.08e-09 1.03 1.3 1.7 4.98
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	682.8	688.8	692.8
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.86	9.86	9.86

MAX_MEAN: 0.129 MAX_MED: 0.0125 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Nilutamide

CHID: 34165 CASRN: 63612-50-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L06

M4ID: 30007912 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.16e-09	0.0278	2.64
sd:	0.000788	1310	6410

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.61e-08	0.798	1.96	1.17	6.37
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	731.88	737.88	741.88
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	20.43	20.43	20.43

MAX_MEAN: 11.2 MAX_MED: 1.64 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tepra loxydim

CHID: 34252 CASRN: 149979-41-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C09

M4ID: 30007745 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.06e-09	1.45	1.17
sd:	1.36e-05	393	43100

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.28e-09	1.35	1.31	1.63	5.14
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	600.5	606.5	610.5
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	11.01	11.01	11.01

MAX_MEAN: 0.536 MAX_MED: 0.175 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Fluroxypyr-meptyl

CHID: 34303 CASRN: 81406-37-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A21

M4ID: 30008310

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	714.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -4.3 MAX_MED: -3.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cyhalofop-butyl

CHID: 34503 CASRN: 122008-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E21

M4ID: 30008163

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	$9.07\text{e-}10$	0.971	1.36
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	$2.64\text{e-}09$	0.642	1.25	1.38	5.84
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	634.69	640.69	644.69
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.83	7.83	7.83

MAX_MEAN: 0.753 MAX_MED: 0.514 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dinotefuran
 CHID: 34549 CASRN: 165252-70-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K08
 M4ID: 30007634 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.52e-09 1.96 1.06
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.37e-08 1.47 1.94 1.86 5.52
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	870.58	876.58	880.58
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	32.75	32.75	32.75

MAX_MEAN: 8.84 MAX_MED: 0.333 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Penoxsulam

CHID: 34803 CASRN: 219714-96-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C18

M4ID: 30008214

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	855.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	25.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -10 MAX_MED: -10 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,2',4,4'-Tetrahydroxybenzophenone

CHID: 41306 CASRN: 131-55-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F11

M4ID: 30007959 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.58e-09	0.909	1.41
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.88e-09	1.29	1.38	1.64	5.18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	710.89	716.89	720.89
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	13.15	13.15	13.15

MAX_MEAN: -0.335 MAX_MED: 0.417 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 5-Ethyl-5-methylhydantoin

CHID: 41368 CASRN: 5394-36-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C16

M4ID: 30008216

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	620.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -4.05 MAX_MED: -4.21 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pentyl butyrate

CHID: 41604 CASRN: 540-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A04

M4ID: 30008276

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	726.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	13.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -6.47 MAX_MED: -2.14 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benodanil

CHID: 41623 CASRN: 15310-01-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D15

M4ID: 30007715

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	750.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	14.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.661 MAX_MED: -1.33 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benzyl cinnamate

CHID: 41663 CASRN: 103-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B20

M4ID: 30008236

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	824.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	22.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-2.33	MAX_MED:	-1.55	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diphenyl phosphite

CHID: 41889 CASRN: 4712-55-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E20

M4ID: 30007974

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	727.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	13.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0262 MAX_MED: -0.443 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Isobornyl propanoate

CHID: 42062 CASRN: 2756-56-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L11

M4ID: 30007661

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.95e-08	2.56	1.84
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.12	0.307	2.3	0.62	14.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	571.06	577.06	580.12
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	8.23	8.23	8.21

MAX_MEAN: 2.22 MAX_MED: 2.27 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: N-Butyl-p-toluenesulfonamide

CHID: 42198 CASRN: 1907-65-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A16

M4ID: 30008264

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	694.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	10.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.423 MAX_MED: 0.756 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dibutyl nonanedioate
 CHID: 44815 CASRN: 2917-73-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A02
 M4ID: 30007796

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	670.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	9.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.58 MAX_MED: -2.82 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 5HPP-33
 CHID: 46970 CASRN: 105624-86-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N02
 M4ID: 30007868 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.7e-10 0.154 1.69
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.41e-08 0.124 2.14 0.455 5.62
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1058.47	1064.47	1068.47
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	19.34	19.34	19.34

MAX_MEAN: 1.31 MAX_MED: 1.41 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: CI-1044

CHID: 47291 CASRN: NOCAS_47291

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G08

M4ID: 30008102

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	673.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	9.71	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3 MAX_MED: -2.68 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Zenarestat

CHID: 47296 CASRN: 112733-06-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L24

M4ID: 30007894

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.85e-10	1.89	1.16
sd:	3.5e-05	1310	63900

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.88e-10	1.41	1.56	2.22	5.62
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	648.07	654.07	658.07
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.16	9.16	9.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.915 MAX_MED: 1.08 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: HMR1426

CHID: 47338 CASRN: 262376-75-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B04

M4ID: 30008252

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	671.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	9.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.74 MAX_MED: -1.15 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: SR271425
 CHID: 47347 CASRN: 155990-20-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J04
 M4ID: 30008034 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.21e-08 2.04 1.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.78e-08 -0.0626 0.773 0.257 10.1
 sd: 0.000544 2970 7990 8590 307000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	772.36	778.36	782.36
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	19.42	19.42	19.42

MAX_MEAN: 1.26 MAX_MED: 2.04 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dexamethasone sodium phosphate
 CHID: 47429 CASRN: 2392-39-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H05
 M4ID: 30007559

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.54e-09	1.77	1.4
sd:	7.56e-05	5440	132000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.6e-09	1.72	1.74	2.29	5.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	573.21	579.21	583.21
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.39	6.39	6.39

MAX_MEAN: 0.374 MAX_MED: 0.56 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benzyloctyl adipate
 CHID: 47528 CASRN: 58394-64-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B14
 M4ID: 30008293

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.56e-09 1.13 1.36
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.07e-09 1.26 1.21 1.63 5.53
 sd: 5.15e-05 15800 63500 10800 156000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	611.1	617.1	621.1
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.88	6.88	6.88

MAX_MEAN: -0.368 MAX_MED: 0.309 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Octylparaben

CHID: 47957 CASRN: 1219-38-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B02

M4ID: 30008254 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1330.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	59.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-2.45	MAX_MED:	-2.34	BMAD:	3.31
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COFF:	9.93	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48507
 CHID: 48507 CASRN: NOCAS_48507
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I13
 M4ID: 30007591

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.73e-10 2.58 2.44
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.13e-09 1.36 0.643 1.78 8.33
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	579.58	585.58	589.58
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.98	5.98	5.98

MAX_MEAN: 2.77 MAX_MED: 3.11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48509

CHID: 48509 CASRN: NOCAS_48509

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B15

M4ID: 30008241

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	841.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	24.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.48 MAX_MED: -3.54 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diphenylmercury(II)
 CHID: 42130 CASRN: 587-85-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E12
 M4ID: 30008172

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.68 2.38 8
 sd: 133 1.12 22.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.44e-08 0.227 3.24 0.498 6.42
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	632.28	637.82	642.28
PROB:	0.94	0.06	0.01
RMSE:	7.53	7.52	7.53

MAX_MEAN: 1.35 MAX_MED: 2.25 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 9 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-(2-Methylbutan-2-yl)phenol
 CHID: 21771 CASRN: 80-46-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A18
 M4ID: 30008262 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 31.2 2.4 8
 sd: 418 0.975 22.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.03e-08 0.793 3.8 1.14 5.39
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	870.49	876.19	880.49
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	28.16	28.13	28.16

MAX_MEAN: 4.59 MAX_MED: 4.03 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benzophenone
 CHID: 21961 CASRN: 119-61-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D18
 M4ID: 30008190

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.9	2.35	8
sd:	123	0.743	10.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.7e-09	1.77	8	2.02	4.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	698.96	703.59	708.96
PROB:	0.9	0.09	0.01
RMSE:	11.33	11.28	11.33

MAX_MEAN: 3.61 MAX_MED: 5.53 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Dodecylphenol
 CHID: 22508 CASRN: 104-43-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A11
 M4ID: 30007787 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.76	1.21	8
sd:	2.57	0.383	18.7

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	31.9	1.42	7.98	1.69	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	776.77	781.58	784.28
PROB:	0.9	0.08	0.02
RMSE:	20.97	20.6	20.56

MAX_MEAN: 19 MAX_MED: 14.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,2-Diphenylethanone
 CHID: 44430 CASRN: 451-40-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L20
 M4ID: 30007898

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	28.6	2.38	8
sd:	290	0.745	9.57

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.48e-10	1.51	5.99	1.91	2.99
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	608.5	611.06	618.5
PROB:	0.78	0.22	0.01
RMSE:	7.06	6.85	7.06

MAX_MEAN: 5.51 MAX_MED: 5.11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.22

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: CI-959
 CHID: 47268 CASRN: 104795-68-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J09
 M4ID: 30007611

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 35.7 2.46 8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 3.97 2.3 8 4.3 1.14
 sd: 60.7 1.64 28.8 202 142

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	627.9	633.15	637.16
PROB:	0.92	0.07	0.01
RMSE:	9.16	9.14	9.14

MAX_MEAN: 1.93 MAX_MED: 1.77 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.08

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Butylphenol
 CHID: 47425 CASRN: 1638-22-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M09
 M4ID: 30007885

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.574 2.8 7.91
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 11.7 1.72 8 1.97 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	696.9	702.9	698.13
PROB:	0.63	0.03	0.34
RMSE:	11.89	11.89	11.21

MAX_MEAN: 14.5 MAX_MED: 15.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.37

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Bisphenol B

CHID: 22442 CASRN: 77-40-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P10

M4ID: 30007770

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.69	1.38	8
sd:	2	0.2	10.8

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.00536	-0.607	8	-0.35	14.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	732.65	724.82	742.65
PROB:	0.02	0.98	0
RMSE:	13.54	12.65	13.54

MAX_MEAN: 15.8 MAX_MED: 16.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.98

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 17alpha-Ethinylestradiol
 CHID: 20576 CASRN: 57-63-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J08
 M4ID: 30007610 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.93	0.824	8
sd:	1.49	0.135	5.37

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.111	-2.22	7.93	-1.91	6.16
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	753	729.36	763
PROB:	0	1	0
RMSE:	15.72	14.11	15.72

MAX_MEAN: 16.4 MAX_MED: 13.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 18 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Progesterone

CHID: 22370 CASRN: 57-83-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M06

M4ID: 30007888

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.9	1.81	8
sd:	2.05	0.0589	3.69

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.01e-12	0.111	7.78	1.02	5.62
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	702.88	686.66	712.88
PROB:	0	1	0
RMSE:	11.24	9.96	11.24

MAX_MEAN: 15.1 MAX_MED: 14.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 18 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8; 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dichlorophen
 CHID: 21824 CASRN: 97-23-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N13
 M4ID: 30008138

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.77	0.695	4.47
sd:	0.567	0.0875	3.99

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.79	0.697	4.41	2.49	10.1
sd:	0.639	0.0887	3.93	1.19	64.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	643.77	477.76	481.75
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	8.05	3.17	3.16

MAX_MEAN: 10.1 MAX_MED: 11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Triclosan

CHID: 32498 CASRN: 3380-34-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091006

M4ID: 30008121

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.23	1.42	8
sd:	0.685	0.101	6.37

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	19	1.44	8	1.71	0.423
sd:	41.1	0.262	14.9	4.36	0.701

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	581.6	495.66	497.44
PROB:	0	0.71	0.29
RMSE:	6.14	3.55	3.56

MAX_MEAN: 9.84 MAX_MED: 10 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,4-Dihydroxy-2-naphthoic acid

CHID: 37730 CASRN: 31519-22-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L09

M4ID: 30007909

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.47	1.87	8
sd:	1.92	0.0665	5.07

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	11.9	1.88	8	4.17	0.301
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	655.41	633.62	637.58
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	9.04	8.06	8.06

MAX_MEAN: 9.15 MAX_MED: 10 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1-Hydroxypyrene

CHID: 38298 CASRN: 5315-79-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H20

M4ID: 30008066

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.44	1.56	8
sd:	2.01	0.142	5.06

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	61.2	0.23	8	0.48	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	763.09	751.46	773.81
PROB:	0	1	0
RMSE:	21.49	19.36	21.51

MAX_MEAN: 55.4 MAX_MED: 68.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diniconazole
 CHID: 40363 CASRN: 83657-24-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C06
 M4ID: 30007748

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.48 1.26 8
 sd: 0.74 0.0421 4.37

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 12.1 1.29 8 2.55 0.619
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	620.3	539.23	541.97
PROB:	0	0.8	0.2
RMSE:	7.26	4.64	4.61

MAX_MEAN: 9.97 MAX_MED: 10.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methyltrioctylammonium chloride

CHID: 44487 CASRN: 5137-55-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A09

M4ID: 30008271

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.05	0.554	8
sd:	0.958	0.233	36

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	11.4	0.572	7.66	3.72	0.3
sd:	25.8	0.176	40.6	3.83	2.77

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	684.8	623.24	626.94
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	10.23	7.1	7.08

MAX_MEAN: 10.2 MAX_MED: 11.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 9-Phenanthroline

CHID: 47592 CASRN: 484-17-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L04

M4ID: 30007914

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.34	0.615	8
sd:	0.844	0.044	12.8

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	24.5	0.666	6.84	0.916	0.348
sd:	31	0.0653	5.74	2.83	0.224

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	654.14	583.26	583.28
PROB:	0	0.5	0.5
RMSE:	9.08	5.93	5.7

MAX_MEAN: 14.9 MAX_MED: 17.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane

CHID: 20375 CASRN: 50-29-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E17

M4ID: 30007977

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.8	0.773	8
sd:	0.876	0.207	8.31

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.37	0.812	8	2.02	18
sd:	1.02	0.217	8.75	0.0583	30.1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	609.47	606.39	599.93
PROB:	0.01	0.04	0.95
RMSE:	8.25	8.11	7.57

MAX_MEAN: 10.7 MAX_MED: 7.44 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 7,12-Dimethylbenz(a)anthracene

CHID: 20510 CASRN: 57-97-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E10

M4ID: 30008174

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	10.1	0.951	5.39
sd:	0.968	0.158	14

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	10.8	0.955	4.14	2.43	2.79
sd:	1.82	0.0864	4.16	0.312	5.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	660.95	581.25	584.08
PROB:	0	0.8	0.2
RMSE:	9.51	6.18	6.1

MAX_MEAN: 11.8 MAX_MED: 10.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Sodium tridecyl sulfate
 CHID: 42418 CASRN: 3026-63-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P04
 M4ID: 30007818

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.99	1.78	8
sd:	1.23	0.0389	3.06

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	21	1.82	8	2.07	1.25
sd:	28.2	0.0505	3.29	0.964	1.49

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	620.25	571.26	571.55
PROB:	0	0.54	0.46
RMSE:	7.48	5.36	5.25

MAX_MEAN: 11.9 MAX_MED: 12.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11; 7

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Biphenyl

CHID: 20161 CASRN: 92-52-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I06

M4ID: 30008056

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	84	1.9	4.45
sd:	2.75	0.0182	0.471

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	84	1.9	4.46	3.33	9.32
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	893.81	620.86	624.86
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	38.33	8.77	8.77

MAX_MEAN: 82.5 MAX_MED: 81.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Cupferron

CHID: 20352 CASRN: 135-20-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D16

M4ID: 30008192

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	59.4	1.91	4.8
sd:	2.99	0.0147	0.838

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	59.4	1.91	4.79	4.26	11.3
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	831.72	612.06	616.06
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	26.07	6.72	6.72

MAX_MEAN: 59 MAX_MED: 59.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: o,p'-DDD
 CHID: 20372 CASRN: 53-19-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K19
 M4ID: 30007923

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 15.4 1.86 8
 sd: 2.96 0.0491 3.38

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 25.9 1.92 8 2.3 17
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	715.3	693.6	693.99
PROB:	0	0.55	0.45
RMSE:	12.61	10.78	10.9

MAX_MEAN: 14.2 MAX_MED: 23.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Endrin

CHID: 20561 CASRN: 72-20-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F15

M4ID: 30007955

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	18.4	0.208	1.44
sd:	0.654	0.0723	0.312

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	20.7	0.287	1.23	4.3	0.383
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	763.82	514.44	517.82
PROB:	0	0.84	0.16
RMSE:	15.39	4.2	4.18

MAX_MEAN: 20.1 MAX_MED: 22.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,2-Diphenylhydrazine
 CHID: 20710 CASRN: 122-66-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C15
 M4ID: 30007739

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	115	1.47	2.23
sd:	2.58	0.0205	0.142

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	115	1.47	2.23	3.87	12.6
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1014.74	617.85	621.85
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	65.88	8.05	8.05

MAX_MEAN: 116 MAX_MED: 115 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Flavone

CHID: 22048 CASRN: 525-82-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G11

M4ID: 30007935 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12	2.06	8
sd:	1.8	0.0678	5.68

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	17.6	2.08	8	2.33	10.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	627.03	600.97	604.87
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	17.41	16.88	16.88

MAX_MEAN: 13.1 MAX_MED: 11.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11; 6; 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Resmethrin

CHID: 22253 CASRN: 10453-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H03

M4ID: 30007557

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14.7	1.94	8
sd:	1.59	0.0276	4.57

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	37.2	2.03	7.98	2.29	17.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	631.12	566.47	568.19
PROB:	0	0.7	0.3
RMSE:	8.55	5.4	5.27

MAX_MEAN: 15.4 MAX_MED: 14.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexylparaben
CHID: 22525 CASRN: 5153-25-3
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L11
M4ID: 30007907 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	53.3	1.84	8
sd:	8.57	0.0574	4.89

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	48.7	0.686	8	0.936	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	991.85	959.87	1006.84
PROB:	0	1	0
RMSE:	56.02	49.37	57.68

MAX_MEAN: 52.6 MAX_MED: 52.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Tromethamine

CHID: 23723 CASRN: 77-86-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M15

M4ID: 30007879

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.5	2	8
sd:	1.33	0.0309	4.48

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	12.5	2	8	3.96	6.17
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	579.77	520.35	524.35
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.56	4.34	4.34

MAX_MEAN: 12.4 MAX_MED: 12.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Pyriproxyfen

CHID: 32640 CASRN: 95737-68-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G21

M4ID: 30007551

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	17.6	1.41	4.02
sd:	0.532	0.0503	1.18

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	31.2	1.49	3.12	2.48	0.327
sd:	50.8	0.079	0.701	4.29	0.681

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	704.09	452.01	453.18
PROB:	0	0.64	0.36
RMSE:	11.69	3.01	2.98

MAX_MEAN: 18.9 MAX_MED: 18.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Azamethiphos
 CHID: 34818 CASRN: 35575-96-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K03
 M4ID: 30007629

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 15.7 1.85 4.48
 sd: 1.55 0.0383 1.25

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 15.7 1.85 4.48 4.3 3.55
 sd: 1.55 0.0383 1.25 839 1520

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	621.17	498.15	502.15
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	8	3.59	3.59

MAX_MEAN: 16.3 MAX_MED: 16.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide

CHID: 37028 CASRN: 57-09-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J13

M4ID: 30008025

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.6	1.91	7.7
sd:	1.11	0.0277	4.34

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	16.1	1.92	7.23	4.14	0.301
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	576.91	481.14	485.11
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.15	3.28	3.28

MAX_MEAN: 12.2 MAX_MED: 12.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dimethylbenzylcarbinylyl acetate

CHID: 41877 CASRN: 151-05-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L15

M4ID: 30007903

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	53.3	1.93	6.57
sd:	1.36	0.00861	1.08

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	67.2	1.96	5.22	2.34	16.2
sd:	15.3	0.0402	1.26	0.00652	11.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	807.7	550.68	552.66
PROB:	0	0.73	0.27
RMSE:	23.19	4.83	4.78

MAX_MEAN: 52.8 MAX_MED: 52.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: SAR 150640

CHID: 47389 CASRN: 433212-21-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M17

M4ID: 30007691

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.6	1.86	8
sd:	1.29	0.028	2.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.4	1.87	8	2.52	4.67
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	631.82	543.33	547.12
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	7.83	4.42	4.42

MAX_MEAN: 13.1 MAX_MED: 14.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: (E)-Anethole
 CHID: 20087 CASRN: 4180-23-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D05
 M4ID: 30008203

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	72.8	1.94	1.21
sd:	10.6	0.114	0.145

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	76.1	1.96	1.23	2.38	16.7
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	836.67	567.54	570.79
PROB:	0	0.84	0.16
RMSE:	25.29	5.66	5.55

MAX_MEAN: 49.6 MAX_MED: 52 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Endosulfan
 CHID: 20560 CASRN: 115-29-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G03
 M4ID: 30007943

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 13.9 1.97 3.04
 sd: 3.01 0.0905 1.21

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 13.9 1.97 3.04 4.05 6.32
 sd: 3.01 0.0905 1.21 101000 354000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	591.9	536.28	540.28
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.53	4.5	4.5

MAX_MEAN: 11.4 MAX_MED: 12.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethoxyquin

CHID: 20582 CASRN: 91-53-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G19

M4ID: 30008091

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	19	1.52	1.62
sd:	1.85	0.0978	0.329

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	32.6	1.92	1.19	2.32	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	691.87	535.37	536.49
PROB:	0	0.64	0.36
RMSE:	11.07	4.49	4.38

MAX_MEAN: 19.6 MAX_MED: 18.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Phenothiazine

CHID: 21126 CASRN: 92-84-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D19

M4ID: 30008189

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.6	2.05	2.8
sd:	7.47	0.235	1.68

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	12.6	2.05	2.8	3.4	6.3
sd:	7.47	0.235	1.67	887	5130

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	593.49	578.17	582.17
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.18	5.95	5.95

MAX_MEAN: 10.8 MAX_MED: 12.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Diphenylamine

CHID: 21975 CASRN: 122-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J18

M4ID: 30008020

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	29.7	1.8	1.8
sd:	2.69	0.0624	0.275

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	29.7	1.8	1.8	3.52	6.74
sd:	2.69	0.0624	0.275	1010	5590

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	720.87	511.61	515.61
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	13.33	3.99	3.99

MAX_MEAN: 27 MAX_MED: 26.6 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,2-Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)-1,1,1-trichloroethane

CHID: 22325 CASRN: 2971-36-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B06

M4ID: 30008301

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	17.8	1.96	1.75
sd:	11.1	0.366	1.01

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	17.8	1.96	1.75	3.53	5.87
sd:	11.1	0.366	1.01	950	4590

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	690.29	660.27	664.27
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	11.58	9.03	9.03

MAX_MEAN: 18.6 MAX_MED: 13.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Phenolphthalin

CHID: 22439 CASRN: 81-90-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N05

M4ID: 30007703

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	47.7	2.19	2.35
sd:	14.1	0.124	0.612

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	47.7	2.19	2.35	3.23	13
sd:	14.1	0.124	0.612	17300	238000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	661.84	510.21	514.21
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	11.37	3.88	3.88

MAX_MEAN: 30.3 MAX_MED: 33.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Benz(a)anthracene

CHID: 23902 CASRN: 56-55-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K02

M4ID: 30007628

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	16.3	1.8	7.81
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	16.7	1.81	7.52	3.72	2.05
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.34	153.61	157.61
PROB:	0.02	0.86	0.12
RMSE:	3.35	2.21	2.21

MAX_MEAN: 14.1 MAX_MED: 14.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.98

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Naphthalenol
 CHID: 27061 CASRN: 135-19-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K10
 M4ID: 30008004

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	40.7	2.53	1.45
sd:	172	2.1	1.72

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	26.2	2.3	1.71	3	7.32
sd:	252	4.84	8.12	148	1580

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	664.51	650.96	655
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	10.56	9.34	9.34

MAX_MEAN: 13.4 MAX_MED: 11.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Potassium perfluorooctanesulfonate
 CHID: 37706 CASRN: 2795-39-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E06
 M4ID: 30007988

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 29.8 2.37 8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 13 2.3 8 3.93 2.49
 sd: 52.3 0.435 11.3 286 462

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	604.88	604.71	608.73
PROB:	0.45	0.49	0.07
RMSE:	7.8	7.81	7.81

MAX_MEAN: 5.42 MAX_MED: 9.99 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.55

FLAGS: 16; 11; 7

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Cyclohexylcyclohexanone

CHID: 40721 CASRN: 92-68-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F12

M4ID: 30008148

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	23	2.32	8
sd:	42.1	0.165	11.9

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	19	2.3	8	4.3	12.6
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	575.25	562.32	566.32
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.87	4.94	4.94

MAX_MEAN: 10.1 MAX_MED: 10.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11; 6

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Hydroxyfluorene
 CHID: 47540 CASRN: 6344-67-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C20
 M4ID: 30008212

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 24.2 2.11 5.98
 sd: 11.8 0.22 7.14

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.9e-08 0.119 7.95 0.501 17.6
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	783.92	774.18	793.92
PROB:	0.01	0.99	0
RMSE:	18.79	16.89	18.79

MAX_MEAN: 25.5 MAX_MED: 20.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 10; 7

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Amino-5-azotoluene
 CHID: 20069 CASRN: 97-56-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F22
 M4ID: 30007755

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	18.7	1.02	8
sd:	2.19	0.0598	16.5

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	22.9	1.07	2.45	2.28	7.23
sd:	3.9	0.114	2.08	0.104	37.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	781.44	724.17	721.26
PROB:	0	0.19	0.81
RMSE:	19.46	13.6	13.33

MAX_MEAN: 23 MAX_MED: 22.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Hexylresorcinol
 CHID: 20699 CASRN: 136-77-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A03
 M4ID: 30007795

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	26	1.11	8
sd:	3.76	0.0649	3.43

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	82.2	1.3	8	1.88	9.24
sd:	6.7	0.0153	7.36	0.0196	3.21

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	872.08	828.87	757.63
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	32.79	23.98	16.22

MAX_MEAN: 71.4 MAX_MED: 80.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Quercetin

CHID: 21218 CASRN: 117-39-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H15

M4ID: 30008071

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	35.2	1.13	7.96
sd:	1.83	0.0517	2.87

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	54.3	1.26	4.91	2.03	3.06
sd:	4.39	0.0192	0.759	0.0296	0.613

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	836.72	673.37	574.58
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	24.87	11.46	5.98

MAX_MEAN: 49 MAX_MED: 49.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,2',6,6'-Tetrachlorobisphenol A

CHID: 21770 CASRN: 79-95-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K15

M4ID: 30007927

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.73	1.25	8
sd:	1.29	0.0953	5.56

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	46.5	1.42	7.79	1.67	2.95
sd:	78.7	0.127	6.46	0.465	2.25

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	685.97	670.85	666.99
PROB:	0	0.13	0.87
RMSE:	13.74	12.42	10.98

MAX_MEAN: 24.3 MAX_MED: 23 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 7; 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Triphenylethylene

CHID: 22320 CASRN: 58-72-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K06

M4ID: 30007632

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	38.7	1.68	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	65.2	0.306	0.835	0.99	17.9
sd:	36.3	0.639	0.406	0.0327	56.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	837.8	793.92	776.28
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	24.18	18.39	17.75

MAX_MEAN: 42.1 MAX_MED: 43.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Octhilinone

CHID: 25805 CASRN: 26530-20-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L06

M4ID: 30007656

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.3	1.13	3.43
sd:	0.89	0.0475	1.11

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	27.5	1.4	1.73	2.03	1.92
sd:	8.62	0.157	0.591	0.121	0.504

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	672.06	527.09	497.14
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	9.83	4.41	3.59

MAX_MEAN: 17 MAX_MED: 18.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol
 CHID: 26602 CASRN: 96-76-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C24
 M4ID: 30008208

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 13.8 1.83 8
 sd: 1.96 0.0554 2.67

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 31.5 1.95 8 2.26 10.4
 sd: 5.98 0.0258 2.14 0.0196 4.16

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	640.15	569.3	521.65
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	9.21	5.42	4.03

MAX_MEAN: 23.1 MAX_MED: 24.5 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 7

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,4-Di-tert-pentylphenol

CHID: 26974 CASRN: 120-95-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L16

M4ID: 30007666

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.93	1.2	2.76
sd:	0.807	0.121	1.31

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	21.9	1.36	7.99	1.68	0.876
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	604.21	529.35	526.94
PROB:	0	0.23	0.77
RMSE:	6.8	4.23	4.07

MAX_MEAN: 11.9 MAX_MED: 11 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11; 7

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 3-Iodo-2-propynyl-N-butylcarbamate

CHID: 28038 CASRN: 55406-53-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M23

M4ID: 30007871

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.75	-0.00821	8
sd:	0.418	0.131	121

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	17.2	0.397	1.58	1.05	0.458
sd:	12.9	0.23	0.443	1.26	0.204

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	590.11	481.25	473.55
PROB:	0	0.02	0.98
RMSE:	6.05	3.26	2.99

MAX_MEAN: 10.9 MAX_MED: 11.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11; 7

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Butralin

CHID: 32337 CASRN: 33629-47-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C17

M4ID: 30007737

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	31.3	0.909	3.74
sd:	1.72	0.0477	1.14

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	35.5	0.95	3.09	2.29	17.6
sd:	2.31	0.0409	0.79	0.0145	36.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	849.65	672.32	651.27
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	26.37	10.5	8.89

MAX_MEAN: 39.9 MAX_MED: 42.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Trifloxystrobin

CHID: 32580 CASRN: 141517-21-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J24

M4ID: 30007626

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.47	0.574	8
sd:	0.598	0.0652	14.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	20.1	0.641	7.89	0.997	0.486
sd:	20.1	0.0674	12.4	1.71	0.281

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	600.24	516.36	507.01
PROB:	0	0.01	0.99
RMSE:	6.61	4	3.68

MAX_MEAN: 10.8 MAX_MED: 11.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11; 7

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4-Nonylphenol

CHID: 33836 CASRN: 104-40-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F10

M4ID: 30007960

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14	1.42	8
sd:	1.31	0.133	7.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	19.9	1.59	4.5	2.17	4.35
sd:	10.6	0.171	2.64	0.2	4.51

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	695.77	624.32	610.95
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	12.42	8.21	7.17

MAX_MEAN: 23.8 MAX_MED: 20.9 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Ethofumesate
 CHID: 34580 CASRN: 26225-79-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K17
 M4ID: 30007643

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 5.86 1.42 8
 sd: 0.614 0.136 7.25

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 15.1 1.68 8 1.93 1.94
 sd: 26.7 0.141 10.2 0.721 0.931

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	553.86	495.34	490.81
PROB:	0	0.09	0.91
RMSE:	5.1	3.54	3.36

MAX_MEAN: 9.52 MAX_MED: 10 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11; 7

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Methylbenzethonium chloride

CHID: 35708 CASRN: 25155-18-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D10

M4ID: 30007720

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.37	0.69	8
sd:	0.927	0.138	10.7

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	25.3	1.01	4.35	1.26	1.11
sd:	25.9	0.0948	5.08	0.729	0.602

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	642.81	609.98	603.81
PROB:	0	0.04	0.96
RMSE:	8.68	7.17	6.79

MAX_MEAN: 13.5 MAX_MED: 12.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 7

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 1,3-Diphenyl-1,3-propanedione

CHID: 41247 CASRN: 120-46-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A17

M4ID: 30008263

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	123	1.63	8
sd:	6.97	0.0873	7.94

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	146	1.62	3.82	2.3	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1054.36	914.25	896.27
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	80.88	37.26	33.16

MAX_MEAN: 139 MAX_MED: 138 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2,2'-(Tetradecylimino)diethanol

CHID: 44865 CASRN: 18924-66-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D10

M4ID: 30008198

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14.1	1.61	8
sd:	1.7	0.102	5.9

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	35.8	1.7	7.51	1.95	1.32
sd:	44.5	0.0555	4.84	0.776	0.844

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	696.89	628.81	627.33
PROB:	0	0.32	0.68
RMSE:	12.28	7.71	7.31

MAX_MEAN: 23.1 MAX_MED: 26.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Sulfonylbis[2-(prop-2-en-1-yl)phenol]

CHID: 47598 CASRN: 41481-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I05

M4ID: 30007583

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.18	1.86	8
sd:	1.12	0.0488	3.71

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13.7	1.94	8	2.28	8.86
sd:	15.3	0.155	10.5	0.0636	31.2

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	552.62	509.45	507.07
PROB:	0	0.23	0.77
RMSE:	5.27	3.84	3.74

MAX_MEAN: 9.2 MAX_MED: 10.3 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11; 7

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Azobenzene
 CHID: 20123 CASRN: 103-33-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C12
 M4ID: 30008220

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 90.7 1.5 2.04
 sd: 6.07 0.0485 0.234

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 121 1.68 1.6 2.33 15.4
 sd: 42.1 0.219 0.375 0.0122 11.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	975.01	701.66	700.28
PROB:	0	0.33	0.67
RMSE:	53.42	11.94	11.78

MAX_MEAN: 97.5 MAX_MED: 105 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: tert-Butylhydroquinone
 CHID: 20220 CASRN: 1948-33-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C21
 M4ID: 30008211

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.92	1.25	2.41
sd:	1.02	0.114	0.885

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	21.8	1.69	1.4	2.1	4.24
sd:	13	0.366	0.479	0.0942	1.51

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	638.9	566.12	543.36
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	7.95	5.4	4.55

MAX_MEAN: 13.9 MAX_MED: 13.8 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dibenzo[1,2-b:4,5-b']difuran
 CHID: 21993 CASRN: 132-64-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P14
 M4ID: 30007774

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	61.5	1.9	3.68
sd:	2.97	0.0189	0.564

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	82.2	1.96	3.5	2.33	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	829.06	573.73	572.28
PROB:	0	0.33	0.67
RMSE:	26.08	5.82	5.64

MAX_MEAN: 56.7 MAX_MED: 58.4 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: 2-Nitroaniline
 CHID: 25726 CASRN: 88-74-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N01
 M4ID: 30007699

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	19	1.92	4.07
sd:	0.881	0.0165	0.834

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	25.9	1.99	3.52	2.33	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	618.55	408.58	408.17
PROB:	0	0.45	0.55
RMSE:	7.97	2.2	2.14

MAX_MEAN: 18.2 MAX_MED: 18.2 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Dodecylphenol

CHID: 27926 CASRN: 27193-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B19

M4ID: 30008288

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.1	0.827	8
sd:	1.78	0.111	4.46

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	61.7	1.74	1.33	1.99	18
sd:	47	0.522	0.504	0.0142	10.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	778.05	734.28	726.9
PROB:	0	0.02	0.98
RMSE:	20.04	15.4	13.82

MAX_MEAN: 31.9 MAX_MED: 40.7 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2492 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Shift_up)

NAME: Hexaconazole

CHID: 34653 CASRN: 79983-71-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078003

M4ID: 30007843

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	10.8	1.23	0.935
sd:	2.69	0.25	0.725

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	20.9	1.81	0.844	2.25	2.48
sd:	11.9	0.567	0.437	0.151	1.36

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	617.44	518.29	514.57
PROB:	0	0.13	0.87
RMSE:	7.23	4.03	3.82

MAX_MEAN: 11.2 MAX_MED: 11.1 BMAD: 3.31

COFF: 9.93 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11